

Multi Sector Assessment MSA KANDAHAR

Nutrition Food Security WASH and Mortality in Kandahar
Province of Afghanistan during January-February 2017

Report done: March 2017

Dr Giorgio M Cortassa MD⁽¹⁾, Dr Ehsan Yawar MD⁽²⁾, Dr Ali Ahmad Stanikzai MD⁽¹⁾

APPENDICES

⁽¹⁾ INTERSOS, Afghanistan Mission ⁽²⁾ HRDA, Kandahar

List of Appendices

- 1) Questionnaires in Pashtun and English
- 2) Field instruction for enumerators in Pashtun and English
- 3) FCS HDDS HHS tables
- 4) Standardization test of enumerators training
- 5) Result Tables for NCHS growth reference 1977
- 6) SMART Plausibility Report
- 7) BARAN NGO last 3 years SAM-OPD activity
- 8) OCHA WWW Operational Presence Dec 2016
- 9) Presence of Health Services “white areas” Handmade Map
- 10) Training schedule
- 11) Results of Phase 1
- 12) List of Villages and PDs with population size for cluster selection

Enumerators' briefing

Appendix 1: Questionnaires in Pashtun and English

په کندهار کې د خوځونې کلاسټر یوه جامع او چټکه ارزونه (MCRA)

ټیم _____ نېټه _____ / / _____
 ولسوالۍ _____ کلي _____ ناحیه _____ GPS _____ / / / _____
 پوښتلېک لټه _____
 آیا زه ستاسو څخه پوښتنې کولای شم؟ هو نه جنس: نارینه ښځینه عمر _____
 د فاهیل په اړه معلومات: خایې اوسیدونکی داخلي بی خایه شوی اسناد لرونکی راستون شوی بېله اسناد لرونکی راستون شوی
 د کورنۍ د اوسیدو د ځای پوښ: خیمه دڅپو جوړ د خینټو جوړ اپارتمان
 آیا روغتیایي خدمتو ته لاسرسی لری؟ هو = 1 لیری دی = 2 پیسی د کهنټ له سببه = 3
 د فاهیل د مشر نوم _____ جنس: نارینه ښځینه عمر _____
 د فاهیل دغو مجموعی شمیر _____

عمر	6-0 میاشتو	6 میاشتو-5 کالو	18-5 کالو	50-18 کالو	50 کالو پورته
نارینه (عمر)					
ښځینه (عمر)					
میننواره یا شیدی					
ورکونکي نسخه					
خوار خواکه؟					
معتول؟					

(FCS/HDDC) دکورنۍ د خوړو د تنوع نمره/د خوړو د مصرف نمره:

زه غواړم ستاسو څخه د مختلفو غذايي توکو په اړه پوښتنې وکړم، کوم چې ستاسو فاهیل پرون او په تیرو 7 ورځو کې خوړلي دي. آیا تاسو راته ویانې شې چې ستاسو د کورنۍ غړي په تیره هفته کې لاندې غذايي مواد یې خوړلي دي؟ (د هرې غذا په هکله د هغه د لمرنی سرچینه او همدارنگه دوهمې سرچینه په هکله پوښتنې وکړی، که چیرې وی.)

غذايي مواد	په هغه ورځو کې چې غذا خوړل شوی		لمرنی سرچینه	دوهمې سرچینه
	پرون	په تیرو 7 ورځو کې		
1: جواړی				
2: وریجی				
3: بوډی/نغم				
4: کچالو				
5: دال، حبوبات او وچه میوه				
6: ماهی				
7: Fish powder				
8: سره غوښه (پسه، اوزده، غوايي)				
9: سپینی غوښی (چرف)				
10: سیزيجاتي غوړی				
11: هگي				
12: شیدی او لیبیات (اصلي غذا)				
13: په چاپو کې لواندازه شیدی				
14: سیزيجات(سره د پايي)				
15: میوه جلت				
16: شیرینی، پوره				

د غذايي موادو د سرچینې کوډ: 1= رانیول 2= خلی تولید 3= تجارتي توکي/خدمتي، تبادلې سوی=3 پور کړل سوی=4 تحفه سوی=5 مرسته شوی غذايي توکي=6 نور(مشخص یی کړی)=7

- (HHS) = کورنۍ د لوړې مرجه: په تیرو څلور هفتو کې (30 ورځو کې) آیا تاسو او یا ستاسو فاهیل:
 0= هېڅ 1= ندرت (1-2 ځلی) 2= بعضی اوقات (3-10 ځلی) اکثره اوقات (اضافه تر 10 ځلی)
 1: پرېشانه سوی یاست چې ستاسو فاهیل به کافی اندازه خواړه و نه لری
 2: د سرچینې له کهنټ له امله نه سی کولای چې هغه خواړه و خوری کوم چې تاسی ترجیح ورکوی.
 3: د سرچینو د کهنټ له امله باید محدود ډول غذا و خوری.
 4: د نورو غذايي موادو د سرچینو د کهنټ له امله هغه غذايي مواد و خوری کوم چې تاسی په واقعیت کې نه غواړی

MSRA-Kandahar

Team # _____ Date ____/____/____ Questionnaire # _____

District _____ Village [] PD [] _____ GPS ____/____/____

Can I interview You? [Y] [N] Respondent _____ sex [M] [F] age _____

HH identification & description Residents [] IDP [] Doc-Returnees [] Undoc-Returnees []

HH type Shelter [] Tent [] Mud [] Brick [] Apartment [] Health Service accessible? [] 1 yes 2 distant 3 money

HH head name _____ sex: [M] [F] age _____ Total persons in the HH: _____

Age	0-6 months	6months-3yy	3-18yy	18-30yy	30+yy
M (yy)					
F (yy)					
PLW					
Mainourish?					
Disable?					

HHDS/FCS: I would like to ask you about different foods that your household members have eaten yesterday and in the last 7 days. Could you please tell me how many days in the past week your household has eaten the following foods? (for each food ask the primary source of each food as well as the second main source, if any)

Food Item	Days eaten		Primary Source	Secondary Source
	Yesterday	Past 7 days		
#1 – Maize				
#2 – Rice				
#3 – Bread/wheat				
#4 – Tubers				
#5 – Groundnuts & Pulses				
#6 – Fish (eaten as a main food)				
#7 – Fish powder (used for flavor only)				
#8 – Red meat (sheep/goat/beef)				
#9 – White meat (poultry)				
#10 – Vegetable oil, fats				
#11 – Eggs				
#12 – Milk and dairy products (main food)				
#13 – Milk in tea in small amounts				
#14 – Vegetables (including leaves)				
#15 – Fruits				
#16 – Sweets, sugar				

Food source codes: Purchase = 1 Own production = 2 Traded goods/services, barter = 3
 Borrowed = 4 Received as gift = 5 Food aid = 6 Other (specify) = 7

HHS: In the past 4 weeks (30 days) did you or any household member:
 Codes: 0 = No 1 = Rarely (1-2 times) 2 = Sometimes (3-10 times) 3 = Often (more than 10 times)

- worry that your household would not have enough food? []
- not able to eat the kinds of foods you preferred because of a lack of resources? []
- have to eat a limited variety of foods due to a lack of resources? []
- have to eat some foods that you really did not want because lack resources for other foods? []
- have to eat a smaller meal than you felt you needed because there was not enough food? []
- have to eat fewer meals in a day because there was not enough food? []
- was there ever no food to eat of any kind in your house because of lack of resources to get food? []
- go to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food? []
- go a whole day and night without eating anything because there was not enough food? []

Appendix 2: Field Instructions for Enumerators in Pashtun and English

د سروی او د پوښتلیک د ښکولو لپاره لارښوونه

1 پړاو: د بیل څخه شروع کول

د ورځني نندې لنډ معلومات (هغه مشکلاتونه چې پرون ورسره مخ سوی پاست، پر مشکلاتو کتنه کول او د حل لاری)

د ترازو اصلاح کول په مجاری وزن سره

د فنټرول چیک لسټ (د هر ټیم لپاره): ترازو، متر، MUAC (5)، پوښتلیک (50)+ تختی میز د لیکلو د پار، د یادښت کتابچه، قلمونه، GPS، د تصادفي نمبر جدول (1)، WHZ او MUAC د قهرست جدول، د روغتیا و مرکز ته د ماشومانو د لیرد فورمه، اسباب د ماشومانو لپاره، هرڅنډه ټیلیفون، دغرمی د بوږی بگس، اوبه + هوټروان، که چیری ټول موجود دی=نو ساحی ته حرکت وکړئ!

د هوټر په نریعه و کلسټر ته رسیدل

د نالیی او یا د کلی د جی بی ایس اصلل او لیگل

رسیدگی وکی و خایی مشرانوته، خلقونه ورته معرفی کړی، د روغتیا د ریاست مکتوب ورښکاره کړی او د همکاري غوښتنه ځنی وکړئ

2 پړاو: په کلسټر کی د کور انتخابول په تصادفي شکل سره:

د کلی او یا د نالیی مرکز ته ورشی، پر مخکه باندی قلم وخرخی او او د قلم د څرکی په تعقیب حرکت وکړی تر څو چې د کلی و پای ته ورسیری، حساب کړی هغه کورونه کم چې ناس پیداکړی پر هغه سړک چې ته ځی، د کلی په اخیر کی ودریږه او قلم بیا وخرخوه تر هغه چې تاته یوه لاره په لاس درکی. اوس هغه تصادفي جدول وگور

ی کومه شمار، تلسو ته ددی کلی لپاره درکول شوی دی. که د مثال په توغه ۷ شمار، وی نو پدی نوی لاره کی بیا کورونه وشمیری تر څو چې ۷ کور ته ورسیری، ددغی اووم کور د راسته طرف څخه سروی شروع کړی او په راسته طرف ادامه ورکړی تر څو چې خپل ټاکلی هدف ته ورسیری.

3 پړاو: په فامیل کی

ده خایی مشرانو په همکاري کورنیو ته لاس رسی کول.

اجازه ځنی واخلی او تشریح ورکړی.

اول خبری وکړی وروسته بی ارزایی کړی

د ماشوم میندی هم په کی ښکول کړی

پوښتلیک: هر کور بی، اخیری صفحه ته وگورئ

آخرنی پوښتنه به د مرگ ومیر په هکله وی.

په ټول پوښتلیک کی: صحیح جواب په X سره وښایست نه په ټکی سره، په یاد واری چې ټکی (.) صحیح نه مطومیری

که چیری د وضاحت غوښتنه سوی بی، (1 یا 2 یا 3، 4) نو هغه انتخاب سوی شمیره په قوس کی ولیکی – مثال [2]

په اوئی برخه کی زموږ هدف دادی چې صحیح سروی وکو او په نه کیفیت سره اندازه واخلو.

دوهم هدف هو دادی چې یو کلسټر په یو ورځ کی تکمیل کړو که نه نو موږ به بیا و همدغی ځای ته راځو چې دا به بیر وخت ونیسئ.

زموږ هدف په یو ورځ کی او په یو کلسټر کی ۱۸ ماشومان دی.

ځانکړی قضی او پیشنهادات

هيڃ نه بدلول، هيڃ نه انتخابول

هيڃ ڪله هم او په هيڃ دليل سره يوه ګورنرني په بله ګورنرني مه بدلولي او هيڃ ڪله هم خپل د خوښي انتخاب مه ګوه ګوم چي ستا له نظره يو ګورنر تر هغه بل ښه دي، هغه ګورنر غريب معلوميري او داسي نور..... که چيري يو دليل داوي چي يو ګورنر تاسي لاس رسي نشي ګولاي (په خاطر د نه همکاري او داسي نور مسائل) پس ياد دانت واخلئ او بل ګورنر ته لارشي.

زيات فائيلونه به يو ګورنر کي:

پدې صورت کي د ګورنرني تعريف تعقيب ګرځي، يوه بله د ظاهر چي اوسيوي (پيښيري) تر يوه چت لاتدي او د يوې اښخوالي د لوبو څخه خوړل کوي.

که چيري په يوه حالت کي ډير زيات فائيلونه په ګورنر کي وي تاسو بايد يوه ګورنرني په تصادفي ډول انتخاب ګرځي. د مثال په ډول، که چيري په يو ګورنر کي ۵ فائيلونه اوسيوي، نو تاسي هر فائيل ته يوه شميره ورکړي او پر کوچني کاغذ بلندي وليکي او په خپل لاس کي يي ونيسي، ده يو نفر څخه غوښته وکړي چي د ټولو کاغذانو څخه يو کاغذ پورته کړي او بيا هغه فائيل سروی کړي او هغه فائيل انتخاب ګرځي.

ټول ماشومان په صحيح توگه اندازه ګرځي:

هميشه ټول ماشومان په صحيح توگه اندازه ګرځي حتی که نو ماشومان غبرګولي وي.

تر ټکلي هدف ډير زيات ماشومان:

هميشه په يو ګورنر کي ټول ماشومان په صحيح توگه اندازه ګرځي، که څه هم تاسي په يو کلسټر کي و خپل ټاکلي هدف ته رسيدلي بايست. نتیجه به يي دغه وي چي په اخريني ګورنر کي تاسي به ډير ماشومان اندازه ګرځي وي. هيڅ مشکل نشته فقط ادامه ورکي.

د کافي ماشومانو نه شتون:

کچيري تاسي په يو کلي او يا ناحيه کي د ګورنريو سروی همکله ګرځي، ماهر بيا هم د ماشومانو ټاکلي تعداد ته نه بايست رسيدلي، دا به هغسي وي چي تاسي بل کلي او يا ناحيه ته د سروی لپاره ورشي، تر څو خپله سروی تکميل ګرځي. ختي وخت داسي په ندرت پيښوي چي تاسي د کلي د ټولو ګورونو څخه ايښه ګرځي وي ماهر بيا هم کافي ماشومانو تعداد هو د سروی لپاره نه وي موندلي. نو بيا تاسي ګولاي شي چي خپل سوپروايزر ته تليفون وکړي او يو نودي کلي ته لار شي. په نودي کلي کي تاسي بيا هم ګورنرني د هغه تصادفي ايتود په طريقه انتخاب ګرځي.

هيڅ ماشوم به يو ګورنرني کي:

هيڅ خبره نه ده، پوښتليک د هغه ګورنرني په هکله پک ګرځي، ماهر د دي ګورنر لپاره به ماشوم نه وي چي اندازه يي د سروی په پاڼه کي وليکوي.

خالې ګرځي:

کچيري په يو ګورنر کي هيڅ څوک نه وي او ګورنر خالي وي نو بادانت يي ګرځي او بل ګورنر ته ور سي. کچيري ګورنر خالي وي اوڅنگ هم شايد تاسي (د هسايه څخه پوښته وکړي) بادانت يي ګرځي او بل ګورنر ته ولاړ سي سروی وکړي او بيا بيرته ورته تاسي کچيري څنگ راغلي وي نو سروی يي وکړي. کچيري ګورنر خالي وي پدې خاطر چي د هغه ګورنر ټول اشخاص هره سوي يي، نو تاسي د هسايه څخه د هغه ګورنر په هکله د پوښتليک پواسطه پوښته وکړي او په اخير کي ددي ګورنرني ټول اشخاص د د مرکز و هير د کچي په برخه کي ثبت ګرځي.

غیر حاضر ماشومان:

کچيري په فائيل کي ماشومان موجود نه وي (هغه ماشومان چي اندازه يي بايد واخلئ شي) ياد دانت يي ګرځي، ماهر دهغه ګورنر په هکله د سروی پوښتياڼه پک ګرځي او بيا پوښته وکړي چي ماشوم کله ګورنر ته راځي. اوس خپل سروی ته ادامه ورکړي ماهر په آخره کي دا مه هيروي چي بيرته دغه ګورنر ته راشي که ماشوم راغلي وي چي اندازه يي واخلئ. هيڅکله يو ماشوم به بل ماشوم مه عوض ګرځي، کچيري د ګورنرني ماشوم د خوړو په مرکز او يا نودي کلينک کي وي نو دا ډيره مهمه ده چي تاسي هغه د خوړو مرکز او يا هغه نودي کلينک ته ورشي او ماشوم اندازه ګرځي، په خاطر ددي چي کيداي شي چي دغه ماشوم خوارځواکه وي. دا کار به حتما وخت نيسي ماهر دا به ډير ښه وي چي تر سره يي ګرځي.

مطلوب ماشومان:

کچیری د یوه کورنی معلول ماشومان عمر د ۶ الی ۳۶ میاشتو پوری وی نو دوی هم باید د نورو ماشومانو په څیر په سروی کی داخل او اندازه شی، کچیری په کوم دلیل سره د ماشوم د بدن اعضا صحیح شکل ونلری او یا هم نور مشکلات ولری او دا د دی سبب کیږی چی تاسی ټولی اندازی واخلئ پس فقط بی یادابنت بی کړی، هغه څه چی امکان لری اندازه بی کړی، (په عمومی توگه زیات وخت مشکلات وی د دوی د قد په اندازه کولو کی وی ماهر عمر، وزن، پروسوب، MAUC اندازه و ثبت کیدای شی.)

4 پړاو: راستنیدل او جواب

خیل پوښتلیک درسه بوسی و HRDA ته

ترازوییا اصلاح کړی.

لنډ معلومات ورکول: مشکلات چی ورسره مخ سوی یاست، د حل لاری، د سیا د پاره پلن

5 پړاو: د معلوماتو ثبت کول او څیرنه کول

پوښتلیک:

(1) د فامیل بیرنډطوی او تشریح

کورنی = د دڅلگو یو گروپ چی د یو چت لاندی ژوند کوی او د یوی آشیزخالی څخه استفاده کوی. د پوښتلیک نمبر: که چیری ستاسو ټیم پرون سروی بی پر ۲۳ نمبر توقف کړی وی پس نن باید تاسو ۲۴ څخه شروع کړی، یخنی په مسلسله توگه سره.

صحنی خدمتو ته لاسرسی درلودل: که چیری دوی په 1 ساعت کی و روغتیایی مرکز ته رسیری د هو جواب لپاره (۱) او کچیری جوان نه وی، د لیری والی په خاطر او د موټر د نه درلودلو په خاطر او یا داسی نورو مسایلو له سببه نوییا په قوس کی (۲) لیگل کیږی. او که د پیسی د کښت او نه موجودیت له سببه وی نو په قوس کی (۳) لیگل کیږی. خلک په هر فامیل کی: عمر بی باید په صحیح توگه په قوس کی ولیگل شی. مثال، (33). PLW: تی ورکونکی او حامله ښځه

معلول: یخنی د بدن حصوه بی قطع شوی وی، نابینا، عصبی ناروغ، د اوریدلو او خیری کولو مشکلات... که چیری تاسو یو شخص ولیدی چی معلول وی، لطفا په (۷۷) سره بی نښتی کړی او په هغه صحیح توگه بی په قوس کی ولیکی.

(2) HHS /FCS/ HDDS دکورنی د خوړو د تنوع نمره/د خوړو د مصرف نمره/ د کورنی د لوړی درجه

تاسی بی خپله هغه د پوښتلیک سوالونه یو په یو تشریح کړی او د دوی جواب په نښه کړی.

(3) VX/BF تی ورکول/ واکسین ورکول.

تاسی نظر مه ورکوی بلکه د پوښتلیکی مطابق د دوی څخه نظر واخلئ او بیا د دوی نظر په پوښتلیک په نښه کړی.

(4) WASH پانی اویه، پاکوالی او حفظ الصحه

تاسی نظر مه ورکوی بلکه د پوښتلیکی مطابق د دوی څخه نظر واخلئ او بیا د دوی نظر په پوښتلیک په نښه کړی.

(5) SMART

په یوه کورنی همیشه هغه ماشومان اندازه کړی چی عمر ونه بی د ۶ میاشتو او ۵۹ میاشتو پوری وی. کچیری یو مور د ماشوم عمر تاسو ته صحیح نه شی ویلی، پس د واکسین کارت بی چیک کړی، او یا مطلی جنتری څخه استفاده وکړی.

کچیری بیا هم د ماشوم سن نه شو معلوم، پس د ټولو ماشومانو قد اندازه کوی او بیا دهغو ماشومانو مکمل اندازه اخلو کوم چی قنونه بی ۶۵۰ او ۱۱۰ سلنتی متر په منځ کی وی.

کچیری په یو کور کی د داسی عمر ماشومان نه وی چی اندازه شی پس د پوښتلیک نوری برخی د هره وایر تر کچی پوری ټک کړی او د کورنی څخه مننه وکړی او د بل کور د سروی لپاره حرکت وکړی.

د اندازه کولو لپاره پروسیجر:

کالی: فقط نازک، کالی او تئیلان، خولی یی باید لیر شی.

پرسوب: O، +، ++، +++

MUAC

خوار خواگه ماشوم باید و یو نودی روختیایی مرکز ه ولیدول شی

د مرگ و میر کچه:

د پوښتیایی مطابق تاسی یی ورته تشریح کری

محلې جتړی - تیر لوی اختر د تاریخ څخه استفاده وکړی، تیر لوی اختر د ۲۰۱۶ کال د سپتمبر په میاشت کی وو.

نیټه باید په داسی شکل وایکل شی چی: 161225 یعنی د ۲۰۱۶ کال د دسمبر د میاشتی ۲۵ نیټه د مړینی د معلوماتو په صورت، تاسی باید د مړینی دقیق ارقام او سبب یی په پوښتیایه کی ولیکی

The questionnaire:

1) HH identification & description

HH = group of people living under the same roof and eating from the same cooking pot

Questionnaire #: the progressive HHs number of your team, i.e. if yesterday you stopped at 23, today you start with 24

Health Service Accessible? In case of need do they feel to be able to swiftly (1h) reach one Health Service for assistance? [1] = yes; [2] no, it is too much distant away for us (we have no car, etc.); [3] no, we do not have money

People in the HH: put the age(s) separated by a dash in the correct place of the table - e.g. 33-42

PLW? Pregnant or Lactating Woman

Malnourish? If they just perceive that the person is malnourished

Disabled? Amputations, blind, mentally impaired, listen/speech problem ... if they perceive that the person is disabled, identify with -yy - in the correct place of the table

2) HDDS/FCS HHS

Self explaining

3) BF Vax

Self explaining

Do NOT suggest the answer! Just ask and take mark of what they say

4) WASH

Self explaining

Do NOT suggest the answer! Just ask and take mark of what they say

5) SMART

We always check all the HH children in the range age 6-59 months (or 65-110 cm if age in months unavailable)

Establish Age: if the mother does not know the age in months, check vaccination booklet, compare to the known age of another child, utilize some well known event in the community for comparison (local calendar)

If it is not possible to know age in months we rapidly screen height and then we measure well all children in the range height 65 to 110 cm

Limit to check height standing or laying down = 87cm (have a control stick)

If there are no children in the correct range: go on, complete the questionnaire, including mortality, say thanks and leave for next HH

Procedures for special cases:

Too many children: once in the HH we always measure ALL the children of the correct age in the HH, even if this means we will end up measuring more children than planned. This is expected.

Too few children: if we complete the cluster and we have NOT reached the expected number of children then we will have to move to the nearest village and to repeat the whole procedure, including HH random sampling. Ask the stakeholder/elder of the first village to accompany you in the nearest village to explain (Then after done please carry him back to his house!!)

Procedures for measuring:

Clothes: only light short and pants, no shoes no caps

Edema 0 + ++ +++

Weight in kg comma 0.1 kg; height in cm comma 0.1 cm; MUAC in mm

Check results with reference table

Refer malnourished children for assistance: we will provide form with data to accompany the child.

6) Mortality

Self explaining, recall period is starting from Eid ul Adha = September 11 2016.

Birthday please use format yy-mm-dd 161225 = 25 December 2016

In case of deaths put the correct number in Cause and Location

Appendix 3: HDDS FCS HHS tables

KAP 2887 ASSESSMENT - FOOD GROUPS TABLE						
Food Item	Days eaten		Primary Source	Secondary Source	FCS	HDDS
	Yesterday	Past Week				
#.1 – Maize					A-2	Cereals
#.2 – Rice					A-2	Cereals
#.3 – Bread/wheat					A-2	Cereals
#.4 – Tubers					A-2	Root and tubers
#.5 – Groundnuts & Pulses					B-3	Pulses
#.6 – Fish (eaten as a main food)					E-4	Fish
#.7 – Fish powder (used for flavor only)					I-0	Miscellaneous
#.8 – Red meat (sheep/goat/beef)					E-4	Meat, poultry, offal
#.9 – White meat (poultry)					E-4	Meat, poultry, offal
#.10 – Vegetable oil, fats					H-0.5	Oil,fats
#.11 – Eggs					E-4	Eggs
#.12 – Milk and dairy products (main food)					F-4	Milk and milk products
#.13 – Milk in tea in small amounts					G-0.5	Miscellaneous
#.14 – Vegetables (including leaves)					C-1	Vegetables
#.15 – Fruits					D-1	Fruits
#.16 – Sweets, sugar					G-0.5	Sugar, honey

outcomes	HDDS	FCS	variety I	variety II
manual calculation				
automatic calculation	0	0	double source	

HHS Household Hunger Score	#
1. worry that your household would not have enough food?	
2. not able to eat the kinds of foods you preferred because of a lack of resources?	
3. have to eat a limited variety of foods due to a lack of resources?	
4. have to eat some foods that you really did not want because lack resources for other foods?	
5. have to eat a smaller meal than you felt you needed because there was not enough food?	
6. have to eat fewer meals in a day because there was not enough food?	
7. was there ever no food to eat of any kind in your house because of lack of resources to get food?	
8. go to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food?	
9. go a whole day and night without eating anything because there was not enough food?	
HHS =	0

In the past 4 weeks (30 days) did you or any household member:

0 = No 1 = Rarely (1–2 times) 2 = Sometimes (3–10 times) 3 = Often (more than 10 times)

Appendix 4: Standardization Test

Standardisation test results

Weight	subjects #	mean kg	SD Kg	Precision			Coef of reliability R (%)	Accuracy		Bias from median Bias (kg)	OUTCOME	
				max kg	Technical error TEM (kg)	TEM/mean TEM (%)		Bias from superv Bias (kg)	result		R value	Bias
Supervisor	11	14.1	3.4	0.1	0.04	0.3	100	-	0.3	TEM good	R value good	
Enumerator 1	11	13.9	3.4	0.2	0.09	0.7	99.9	-0.15	0.14	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 2	11	13.9	3.4	0.2	0.07	0.5	100	-0.17	0.13	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 3	11	13.9	3.4	0.3	0.12	0.9	99.9	-0.15	0.14	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 4	11	14	3.4	0.1	0.05	0.4	100	-0.1	0.19	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 5	11	13.9	3.4	0.1	0.06	0.4	100	-0.15	0.14	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 6	11	13.9	3.4	0.3	0.12	0.8	99.9	-0.15	0.15	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 7	11	14	3.4	0.3	0.12	0.9	99.9	-0.08	0.22	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 8	11	14.1	3.4	0.2	0.1	0.7	99.9	-0.05	0.25	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 9	11	14	3.4	0.3	0.1	0.7	99.9	-0.08	0.21	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 10	11	14	3.4	0.3	0.12	0.8	99.9	-0.12	0.17	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 11	11	14	3.4	0.3	0.14	1	99.8	-0.1	0.19	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 12	11	14	3.4	0.2	0.08	0.5	99.9	-0.1	0.2	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 13	11	14	3.5	0.2	0.07	0.5	100	-0.07	0.22	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 14	11	14	3.5	0.3	0.1	0.7	99.9	-0.1	0.2	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 15	11	14	3.5	0.3	0.09	0.7	99.9	-0.07	0.22	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 16	11	14	3.5	0.3	0.1	0.7	99.9	-0.08	0.21	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 17	11	14	3.5	0.3	0.12	0.9	99.9	-0.13	0.16	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good

Enumerator 18	11	14	3.5	0.3	0.1	0.7	99.9	-0.12	0.18	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 19	11	14	3.4	0.2	0.09	0.7	99.9	-0.08	0.21	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 20	11	14	3.4	0.1	0.06	0.4	100	-0.09	0.2	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
enum inter 1st	20x11	14	3.4	-	0.13	0.9	99.9	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	
enum inter 2nd	20x11	14	3.4	-	0.11	0.8	99.9	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	
inter enum + sup	21x11	14	3.4	-	0.12	0.8	99.9	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	
TOTAL intra+inter	20x11	-	-	-	0.15	1.1	99.8	-0.11	0.19	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
TOTAL+ sup	21x11	-	-	-	0.15	1.1	99.8	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	

Height	subjects	mean	SD	max	Technical error	TEM/mean	Coef of reliability	Bias from superv	Bias from median	result		
	#	cm	Cm	cm	TEM (cm)	TEM (%)	R (%)	Bias (cm)	Bias (cm)			
Supervisor	11	91.8	11.5	0.6	0.16	0.2	100	-	-0.07	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 1	11	92	11.4	0.6	0.25	0.3	100	0.2	0.13	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 2	11	91.8	11.3	1	0.36	0.4	99.9	-0.05	-0.13	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 3	11	91.6	11.7	0.7	0.34	0.4	99.9	-0.18	-0.25	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 4	11	91.2	11.8	1.8	0.47	0.5	99.8	-0.62	-0.7	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 5	11	91.2	11.8	0.7	0.26	0.3	99.9	-0.61	-0.68	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 6	11	91.1	11.7	1	0.36	0.4	99.9	-0.69	-0.76	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 7	11	91.7	11.7	0.8	0.3	0.3	99.9	-0.16	-0.24	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 8	11	91.7	11.5	0.8	0.36	0.4	99.9	-0.15	-0.22	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 9	11	91.9	11.6	0.8	0.39	0.4	99.9	0.05	-0.02	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 10	11	91.8	11.4	1.7	0.52	0.6	99.8	-0.03	-0.1	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good

Enumerator 11	11	91.8	11.3	1.6	0.54	0.6	99.8	-0.07	-0.15	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 12	11	91.8	11.3	1.8	0.61	0.7	99.7	0.01	-0.06	TEM poor	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 13	11	92	11.3	0.9	0.34	0.4	99.9	0.14	0.07	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 14	11	91.8	11.4	0.7	0.29	0.3	99.9	0.01	-0.06	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 15	11	91.9	11.5	0.8	0.34	0.4	99.9	0.05	-0.03	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 16	11	91.9	11.5	0.7	0.32	0.3	99.9	0.03	-0.04	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 17	11	91.8	11.5	0.8	0.3	0.3	99.9	0.01	-0.06	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 18	11	91.9	11.5	0.7	0.26	0.3	99.9	0.05	-0.02	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 19	11	91.9	11.4	0.7	0.35	0.4	99.9	0.1	0.03	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 20	11	92	11.4	1	0.3	0.3	99.9	0.15	0.08	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
enum inter 1st	20x11	91.7	11.3	-	0.73	0.8	99.6	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	
enum inter 2nd	20x11	91.7	11.3	-	0.5	0.5	99.8	-	-	TEM good	R value good	
inter enum + sup	21x11	91.7	11.3	-	0.6	0.7	99.7	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	
TOTAL intra+inter	20x11	-	-	-	0.73	0.8	99.6	-0.09	-0.16	TEM acceptable	R value good	Bias good
TOTAL+ sup	21x11	-	-	-	0.71	0.8	99.6	-	-	TEM acceptable	R value good	

MUAC	subjects	mean	SD	max	Technical error	TEM/mean	Coef of reliability	Bias from superv	Bias from median	result		
	#	mm	mm	mm	TEM (mm)	TEM (%)	R (%)	Bias (mm)	Bias (mm)			
Supervisor	11	161.2	7.5	2	0.67	0.4	99.2	-	1.18	TEM good	R value good	
Enumerator 1	11	161	8.3	3	1.04	0.6	98.4	-0.18	1	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 2	11	160.3	8.3	2	0.85	0.5	98.9	-0.91	0.27	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good

Enumerator 3	11	160.8	8	2	0.74	0.5	99.1	-0.36	0.82	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 4	11	160.6	7.5	3	1.11	0.7	97.8	-0.59	0.59	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 5	11	160.2	7.5	4	1.22	0.8	97.3	-0.95	0.23	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 6	11	159.4	7.5	3	1.13	0.7	97.8	-1.82	-0.64	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 7	11	161.4	7.8	1	0.43	0.3	99.7	0.18	1.36	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 8	11	161.4	8.2	3	0.85	0.5	98.9	0.18	1.36	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 9	11	161.5	7.9	4	1.21	0.7	97.7	0.36	1.55	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 10	11	161.1	7.8	1	0.37	0.2	99.8	-0.05	1.14	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 11	11	160.8	7.4	3	0.85	0.5	98.7	-0.36	0.82	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 12	11	160.6	7.9	3	1.19	0.7	97.7	-0.59	0.59	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 13	11	161.3	7.6	3	1.15	0.7	97.7	0.14	1.32	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 14	11	161.2	7.7	5	1.24	0.8	97.4	0	1.18	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 15	11	160.9	7.5	2	0.6	0.4	99.4	-0.27	0.91	TEM good	R value good	Bias good
Enumerator 16	11	161	7.8	3	0.9	0.6	98.6	-0.18	1	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 17	11	161.5	7.3	3	1.17	0.7	97.4	0.27	1.45	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 18	11	161.4	7.7	2	1.09	0.7	98	0.18	1.36	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 19	11	161.4	7.9	3	1.19	0.7	97.7	0.23	1.41	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
Enumerator 20	11	161.2	7.7	4	1.28	0.8	97.2	0	1.18	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
enum inter 1st	20x11	160.9	7.7	-	1.37	0.9	96.8	-	-	TEM good	R value acceptable	
enum inter 2nd	20x11	161	7.6	-	1.28	0.8	97.2	-	-	TEM good	R value acceptable	
inter enum + sup	21x11	161	7.6	-	1.31	0.8	97.1	-	-	TEM good	R value acceptable	
TOTAL intra+inter	20x11	-	-	-	1.67	1	95.2	-0.24	0.96	TEM good	R value acceptable	Bias good
TOTAL+ sup	21x11	-	-	-	1.65	1	95.3	-	-	TEM good	R value acceptable	

Suggested cut-off points for acceptability of measurements

	MUAC mm	Weight Kg	Height cm	Parameter
Good	<2.0	<0.04	<0.4	individual
Acceptable	<2.7	<0.10	<0.6	TEM
Poor	<3.3	<0.21	<1.0	(intra)
Reject	>3.3	>0.21	>1.0	
Good	<2.0	<0.10	<0.5	Team TEM
Acceptable	<2.7	<0.21	<1.0	(intra+inter)
Poor	<3.3	<0.24	<1.5	and Total
Reject	>3.3	>0.24	>1.5	
Good	>99	>99	>99	R value
Acceptable	>95	>95	>95	
Poor	>90	>90	>90	
Reject	<90	<90	<90	
Good	<1	<0.04	<0.4	Bias
Acceptable	<2	<0.10	<0.6	From sup if good
Poor	<3	<0.21	<1.4	outcome, otherwise
Reject	>3	>0.21	>1.4	from median
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****
****	****	****	****	****

Appendix 5: Result Tables for NCHS growth reference 1977

Table 5.1: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on weight-for-height z-scores (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 1251	Boys n = 641	Girls n = 610
Prevalence of global malnutrition (<-2 z-score and/or oedema)	(106) 8.5 % (6.0 - 11.8 95% C.I.)	(66) 10.3 % (7.1 - 14.6 95% C.I.)	(40) 6.6 % (4.3 - 9.9 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score, no oedema)	(88) 7.0 % (4.8 - 10.2 95% C.I.)	(54) 8.4 % (5.5 - 12.6 95% C.I.)	(34) 5.6 % (3.6 - 8.6 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (<-3 z-score and/or oedema)	(18) 1.4 % (0.8 - 2.7 95% C.I.)	(12) 1.9 % (0.9 - 3.9 95% C.I.)	(6) 1.0 % (0.4 - 2.4 95% C.I.)

The prevalence of oedema is 0.7 %

Table 5.2: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on weight-for-height z-scores and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate wasting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	288	5	1.7	38	13.2	242	84.0	3	1.0
18-29	304	4	1.3	26	8.6	269	88.5	5	1.6
30-41	302	0	0.0	18	6.0	283	93.7	1	0.3
42-53	267	0	0.0	3	1.1	264	98.9	0	0.0
54-59	90	0	0.0	3	3.3	87	96.7	0	0.0
Total	1251	9	0.7	88	7.0	1145	91.5	9	0.7

Table 5.3: Distribution of acute malnutrition and oedema based on weight-for-height z-scores

	<-3 z-score	>=-3 z-score
Oedema present	Marasmic kwashiorkor No. 1 (0.1 %)	Kwashiorkor No. 8 (0.6 %)
Oedema absent	Marasmic No. 11 (0.9 %)	Not severely malnourished No. 1240 (98.4 %)

Table 5.4: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on MUAC cut off's (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 1268	Boys n = 647	Girls n = 621
Prevalence of global malnutrition (< 125 mm and/or oedema)	(183) 14.4 % (11.8 - 17.5 95% C.I.)	(94) 14.5 % (11.4 - 18.3 95% C.I.)	(89) 14.3 % (11.0 - 18.5 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (< 125 mm and >= 115 mm, no oedema)	(140) 11.0 % (8.7 - 13.9 95% C.I.)	(72) 11.1 % (8.3 - 14.7 95% C.I.)	(68) 11.0 % (8.1 - 14.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (< 115 mm and/or oedema)	(43) 3.4 % (2.4 - 4.7 95% C.I.)	(22) 3.4 % (2.2 - 5.3 95% C.I.)	(21) 3.4 % (2.1 - 5.3 95% C.I.)

Table 5.5: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on MUAC cut off's and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (< 115 mm)		Moderate wasting (>= 115 mm and < 125 mm)		Normal (>= 125 mm)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	296	20	6.8	79	26.7	197	66.6	3	1.0
18-29	312	8	2.6	40	12.8	264	84.6	5	1.6
30-41	302	2	0.7	14	4.6	286	94.7	1	0.3
42-53	268	4	1.5	5	1.9	259	96.6	0	0.0
54-59	90	1	1.1	3	3.3	86	95.6	0	0.0
Total	1268	35	2.8	141	11.1	1092	86.1	9	0.7

Table 5.6: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on the percentage of the median and/or oedema

	n = 1251
Prevalence of global acute malnutrition (<80% and/or oedema)	(55) 4.4 % (3.1 - 6.1 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate acute malnutrition (<80% and >= 70%, no oedema)	(45) 3.6 % (2.6 - 5.0 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition (<70% and/or oedema)	(10) 0.8 % (0.3 - 1.9 95% C.I.)

Table 5.7: Prevalence of malnutrition by age, based on weight-for-height percentage of the median and oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (<70% median)		Moderate wasting (>=70% and <80% median)		Normal (>=80% median)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	288	0	0.0	22	7.6	263	91.3	3	1.0
18-29	304	1	0.3	16	5.3	282	92.8	5	1.6
30-41	302	0	0.0	6	2.0	295	97.7	1	0.3
42-53	267	0	0.0	0	0.0	267	100.0	0	0.0
54-59	90	0	0.0	1	1.1	89	98.9	0	0.0
Total	1251	1	0.1	45	3.6	1196	95.6	9	0.7

Table 5.8: Prevalence of underweight based on weight-for-age z-scores by sex

	All n = 1240	Boys n = 631	Girls n = 609
Prevalence of underweight (<-2 z-score)	(386) 31.1 % (26.7 - 35.9 95% C.I.)	(206) 32.6 % (27.8 - 37.9 95% C.I.)	(180) 29.6 % (24.2 - 35.5 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate underweight (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(298) 24.0 % (20.6 - 27.9 95% C.I.)	(158) 25.0 % (21.0 - 29.6 95% C.I.)	(140) 23.0 % (18.6 - 28.0 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe underweight (<-3 z-score)	(88) 7.1 % (5.5 - 9.2 95% C.I.)	(48) 7.6 % (5.3 - 10.8 95% C.I.)	(40) 6.6 % (4.7 - 9.1 95% C.I.)

Table 5.9: Prevalence of underweight by age, based on weight-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe underweight (<-3 z-score)		Moderate underweight (>=-3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (>= -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	284	26	9.2	75	26.4	183	64.4	3	1.1
18-29	295	24	8.1	77	26.1	194	65.8	5	1.7
30-41	302	26	8.6	72	23.8	204	67.5	1	0.3
42-53	269	5	1.9	55	20.4	209	77.7	0	0.0
54-59	90	7	7.8	19	21.1	64	71.1	0	0.0
Total	1240	88	7.1	298	24.0	854	68.9	9	0.7

Table 5.10: Prevalence of stunting based on height-for-age z-scores and by sex

	All n = 1181	Boys n = 593	Girls n = 588
Prevalence of stunting (<-2 z-score)	(552) 46.7 % (43.0 - 50.5 95% C.I.)	(277) 46.7 % (42.3 - 51.2 95% C.I.)	(275) 46.8 % (41.4 - 52.2 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate stunting (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(346) 29.3 % (26.3 - 32.4 95% C.I.)	(170) 28.7 % (24.9 - 32.8 95% C.I.)	(176) 29.9 % (26.1 - 34.1 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe stunting (<-3 z-score)	(206) 17.4 % (14.6 - 20.8 95% C.I.)	(107) 18.0 % (14.4 - 22.4 95% C.I.)	(99) 16.8 % (13.3 - 21.0 95% C.I.)

Table 5.11: Prevalence of stunting by age based on height-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe stunting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate stunting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	271	21	7.7	54	19.9	196	72.3
18-29	286	51	17.8	94	32.9	141	49.3
30-41	279	66	23.7	96	34.4	117	41.9
42-53	259	47	18.1	81	31.3	131	50.6
54-59	86	21	24.4	21	24.4	44	51.2
Total	1181	206	17.4	346	29.3	629	53.3

Table 5.12: Prevalence of overweight based on weight for height cut off's and by sex (no oedema)

	All n = 1251	Boys n = 641	Girls n = 610
Prevalence of overweight (WHZ > 2)	(16) 1.3 % (0.8 - 2.1 95% C.I.)	(9) 1.4 % (0.7 - 2.8 95% C.I.)	(7) 1.1 % (0.6 - 2.3 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe overweight (WHZ > 3)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)

Table 5.13: Prevalence of overweight by age, based on weight for height (no oedema)

Age (mo)	Total no.	Overweight (WHZ > 2)		Severe Overweight (WHZ > 3)	
		No.	%	No.	%
6-17	288	4	1.4	0	0.0
18-29	304	6	2.0	0	0.0
30-41	302	4	1.3	0	0.0
42-53	267	2	0.7	0	0.0
54-59	90	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total	1251	16	1.3	0	0.0

Table 5.14: Mean z-scores, Design Effects and excluded subjects

Indicator	n	Mean z-scores \pm SD	Design Effect (z-score < -2)	z-scores not available*	z-scores out of range
Weight-for-Height	1242	-0.49 \pm 1.05	3.35	21	9
Weight-for-Age	1240	-1.46 \pm 1.07	3.10	14	18
Height-for-Age	1181	-1.86 \pm 1.19	1.67	0	91

* contains for WHZ and WAZ the children with edema.

Appendix 6: Plausibility Report ENA

Plausibility check for: 0-AFN-KDH-INTRS-HRDA(Full).as

Standard/Reference used for z-score calculation: WHO standards 2006

(If it is not mentioned, flagged data is included in the evaluation. Some parts of this plausibility report are more for advanced users and can be skipped for a standard evaluation)

Overall data quality

Criteria	Flags*	Unit	Excel.	Good	Accept	Problematic	Score
Flagged data (% of out of range subjects)	Incl	%	0-2.5 0	>2.5-5.0 5	>5.0-7.5 10	>7.5 20	0 (2.5 %)
Overall Sex ratio (Significant chi square) (p=0.432)	Incl	p	>0.1 0	>0.05 2	>0.001 4	<=0.001 10	0
Age ratio(6-29 vs 30-59) (Significant chi square)	Incl	p	>0.1 0	>0.05 2	>0.001 4	<=0.001 10	0 (p=0.167)
Dig pref score - weight	Incl	#	0-7	8-12 0 2	13-20	> 20 4 10	0 (7)
Dig pref score - height	Incl	#	0-7	8-12 0 2	13-20	> 20 4 10	0 (7)
Dig pref score - MUAC	Incl	#	0-7	8-12 0 2	13-20	> 20 4 10	0 (7)
Standard Dev WHZ .	Excl	SD	<1.1	<1.15 and	<1.20 and	>=1.20 or	
.	Excl	SD	>0.9 0	>0.85 5	>0.80 10	<=0.80 20	5 (1.15)
Skewness WHZ	Excl	#	<±0.2	<±0.4 0 1	<±0.6	>=±0.6 3 5	0 (-0.12)
Kurtosis WHZ	Excl	#	<±0.2	<±0.4 0 1	<±0.6	>=±0.6 3 5	3 (-0.47)
Poisson dist WHZ-2	Excl	p	>0.05 0	>0.01 1	>0.001 3	<=0.001 5	5 (p=0.000)
OVERALL SCORE WHZ =			0-9	10-14	15-24	>25	13 %

The overall score of this survey is 13 %, this is good.

There were no duplicate entries detected.

Percentage of children with no exact birthday: 95 %

Anthropometric Indices likely to be in error (-3 to 3 for WHZ, -3 to 3 for HAZ, -3 to 3 for WAZ, from observed mean - chosen in Options panel - these values will be flagged and should be excluded from analysis for a nutrition survey in emergencies. For other surveys this might not be the best procedure e.g. when the percentage of overweight children has to be calculated):

Line=15/ID=15: HAZ (-5.071), Age may be incorrect
Line=53/ID=53: HAZ (-5.994), Age may be incorrect
Line=55/ID=55: HAZ (-5.322), Age may be incorrect
Line=68/ID=68: HAZ (1.457), Age may be incorrect
Line=79/ID=80: HAZ (-5.324), Height may be incorrect
Line=85/ID=86: **WHZ (3.406)**, HAZ (-5.231), Height may be incorrect
Line=99/ID=101: HAZ (2.204), Height may be incorrect
Line=132/ID=134: HAZ (-5.324), Age may be incorrect
Line=142/ID=145: **WHZ (-3.775)**, HAZ (1.127), Height may be incorrect
Line=177/ID=181: **WHZ (3.482)**, HAZ (-6.316), Height may be incorrect
Line=204/ID=210: HAZ (-6.193), Age may be incorrect
Line=207/ID=213: HAZ (-4.912), Age may be incorrect
Line=208/ID=214: HAZ (-6.777), Height may be incorrect
Line=211/ID=217: HAZ (-6.346), Age may be incorrect
Line=221/ID=227: **WHZ (3.129)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=265/ID=275: **WHZ (-3.565)**, HAZ (-5.185), WAZ (-5.187)
Line=271/ID=282: **WHZ (-3.615)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=278/ID=292: HAZ (1.138), Height may be incorrect
Line=308/ID=322: HAZ (7.603), WAZ (2.945), Age may be incorrect
Line=309/ID=323: HAZ (-5.007), WAZ (-4.687), Age may be incorrect
Line=323/ID=337: **WHZ (3.620)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=329/ID=343: HAZ (-5.866), Height may be incorrect
Line=335/ID=349: HAZ (-5.088), Age may be incorrect
Line=340/ID=354: HAZ (-5.918), Age may be incorrect
Line=347/ID=372: HAZ (-4.987), Age may be incorrect
Line=372/ID=399: **WHZ (-3.508)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=375/ID=402: HAZ (-5.689), Age may be incorrect
Line=377/ID=404: HAZ (-5.604), Height may be incorrect
Line=409/ID=436: HAZ (-5.572), WAZ (-4.814), Age may be incorrect
Line=410/ID=437: HAZ (-5.467), Age may be incorrect
Line=411/ID=438: HAZ (-4.998), Height may be incorrect
Line=422/ID=450: **WHZ (2.946)**, HAZ (-5.261), Height may be incorrect
Line=449/ID=477: WAZ (-4.253), Weight may be incorrect
Line=451/ID=479: HAZ (-6.383), Age may be incorrect
Line=484/ID=512: **WHZ (-3.704)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=498/ID=529: **WHZ (3.135)**, HAZ (-6.005), Height may be incorrect
Line=508/ID=540: HAZ (-4.966), Age may be incorrect
Line=511/ID=543: **WHZ (3.200)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=578/ID=611: HAZ (-5.277), Age may be incorrect
Line=579/ID=612: **WHZ (-3.577)**, WAZ (-4.700), Weight may be incorrect
Line=580/ID=613: HAZ (-5.029), Age may be incorrect
Line=600/ID=636: **WHZ (3.759)**, Height may be incorrect
Line=621/ID=657: HAZ (-6.244), Age may be incorrect
Line=652/ID=688: HAZ (1.167), Height may be incorrect
Line=661/ID=697: **WHZ (3.246)**, Height may be incorrect
Line=676/ID=712: **WHZ (-3.516)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=687/ID=723: **WHZ (-3.705)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=710/ID=746: HAZ (2.211), Height may be incorrect
Line=711/ID=747: HAZ (2.698), Height may be incorrect

Line=713/ID=749: HAZ (2.200), Height may be incorrect
Line=714/ID=750: HAZ (1.389), Height may be incorrect
Line=715/ID=751: HAZ (2.805), Height may be incorrect
Line=717/ID=753: HAZ (4.768), Height may be incorrect
Line=718/ID=754: HAZ (1.954), Height may be incorrect
Line=720/ID=756: HAZ (4.608), Age may be incorrect
Line=737/ID=771: **WHZ (3.541)**, Height may be incorrect
Line=786/ID=824: HAZ (-5.045), Age may be incorrect
Line=825/ID=864: HAZ (-5.238), WAZ (-4.289), Age may be incorrect
Line=834/ID=873: **WHZ (2.823)**, Height may be incorrect
Line=837/ID=876: HAZ (2.171), Height may be incorrect
Line=843/ID=884: **WHZ (-4.462)**, WAZ (-4.519), Weight may be incorrect
Line=855/ID=896: HAZ (-5.320), Age may be incorrect
Line=908/ID=951: **WHZ (-3.698)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=937/ID=980: HAZ (3.044), Height may be incorrect
Line=940/ID=983: HAZ (1.304), Height may be incorrect
Line=944/ID=987: HAZ (1.951), Height may be incorrect
Line=948/ID=991: HAZ (2.286), Height may be incorrect
Line=960/ID=1004: **WHZ (-4.094)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1013/ID=1057: WAZ (2.196), Weight may be incorrect
Line=1037/ID=1081: HAZ (-5.064), Age may be incorrect
Line=1049/ID=1093: HAZ (-5.461), Age may be incorrect
Line=1073/ID=1117: HAZ (-5.213), Age may be incorrect
Line=1095/ID=1139: HAZ (-5.314), Age may be incorrect
Line=1139/ID=1183: HAZ (-5.824), Age may be incorrect
Line=1161/ID=1205: HAZ (1.254), Age may be incorrect
Line=1165/ID=1209: **WHZ (-3.218)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1194/ID=1239: HAZ (-5.182), Age may be incorrect
Line=1215/ID=1261: **WHZ (3.142)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1222/ID=1268: HAZ (1.951), Age may be incorrect
Line=1227/ID=1273: HAZ (2.815), WAZ (2.289), Age may be incorrect
Line=1235/ID=1281: HAZ (3.818), WAZ (1.956), Age may be incorrect
Line=1254/ID=1300: HAZ (-5.122), Age may be incorrect
Line=1304/ID=1350: **WHZ (3.179)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1305/ID=1351: HAZ (-5.802), Age may be incorrect
Line=1307/ID=1353: **WHZ (3.093)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1315/ID=1361: **WHZ (3.235)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1329/ID=1375: **WHZ (-3.312)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1337/ID=1383: **WHZ (3.534)**, HAZ (-6.029), Height may be incorrect
Line=1345/ID=1393: HAZ (3.864), WAZ (2.394), Age may be incorrect
Line=1349/ID=1397: HAZ (1.211), Age may be incorrect
Line=1352/ID=1400: **WHZ (2.998)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1356/ID=1404: **WHZ (3.315)**, Weight may be incorrect
Line=1370/ID=1420: HAZ (1.628), Height may be incorrect
Line=1372/ID=1422: HAZ (2.826), Height may be incorrect
Line=1374/ID=1424: HAZ (2.377), Height may be incorrect
Line=1378/ID=1428: HAZ (5.344), Age may be incorrect
Line=1382/ID=1432: HAZ (4.834), Age may be incorrect
Line=1385/ID=1435: HAZ (3.656), Height may be incorrect
Line=1386/ID=1436: **WHZ (-3.674)**, HAZ (2.932), Height may be incorrect

Line=1389/ID=1439:	HAZ (4.083), Age may be incorrect
Line=1390/ID=1440:	HAZ (3.889), Height may be incorrect
Line=1393/ID=1443:	HAZ (8.318), WAZ (2.400), Age may be incorrect
Line=1396/ID=1447:	HAZ (8.560), WAZ (2.427), Age may be incorrect
Line=1399/ID=1450:	HAZ (8.682), WAZ (2.398), Age may be incorrect
Line=1402/ID=1453:	HAZ (7.247), Age may be incorrect
Line=1403/ID=1454:	HAZ (6.586), WAZ (1.947), Age may be incorrect
Line=1406/ID=1457:	HAZ (7.273), Age may be incorrect
Line=1407/ID=1458:	HAZ (5.102), Age may be incorrect
Line=1410/ID=1463:	HAZ (4.860), Age may be incorrect
Line=1411/ID=1464:	HAZ (1.492), Age may be incorrect
Line=1413/ID=1466:	HAZ (5.105), Age may be incorrect
Line=1414/ID=1467:	HAZ (4.185), Age may be incorrect
Line=1416/ID=1469:	HAZ (4.007), Height may be incorrect
Line=1418/ID=1471:	HAZ (2.696), Height may be incorrect
Line=1420/ID=1473:	HAZ (8.581), WAZ (2.159), Age may be incorrect
Line=1421/ID=1474:	HAZ (4.133), Age may be incorrect
Line=1425/ID=1478:	HAZ (2.079), Height may be incorrect
Line=1427/ID=1480:	HAZ (8.360), WAZ (2.049), Age may be incorrect
Line=1428/ID=1481:	HAZ (8.016), WAZ (2.342), Age may be incorrect
Line=1429/ID=1482:	HAZ (1.976), Height may be incorrect
Line=1432/ID=1485:	HAZ (1.325), Height may be incorrect
Line=1433/ID=1486:	HAZ (8.030), WAZ (2.309), Age may be incorrect
Line=1436/ID=1489:	HAZ (9.618), WAZ (2.764), Age may be incorrect
Line=1440/ID=1493:	HAZ (8.318), WAZ (2.543), Age may be incorrect

Percentage of values flagged with SMART flags:WHZ: 2.5 %, HAZ: 7.7 %, WAZ: 1.7 %

Age distribution:

- Month 6 : ##
- Month 7 : #####
- Month 8 : #####
- Month 9 : #####
- Month 10 : #####
- Month 11 : #####
- Month 12 : #####
- Month 13 : #####
- Month 14 : #####
- Month 15 : #####
- Month 16 : #####
- Month 17 : #####
- Month 18 : #####
- Month 19 : #####
- Month 20 : #####
- Month 21 : #####
- Month 22 : #####
- Month 23 : #####

Month 24 : #####
 Month 25 : #####
 Month 26 : #####
 Month 27 : #####
 Month 28 : #####
 Month 29 : #####
 Month 30 : #####
 Month 31 : #####
 Month 32 : #####
 Month 33 : #####
 Month 34 : #####
 Month 35 : #####
 Month 36 : #####
 Month 37 : #####
 Month 38 : #####
 Month 39 : #####
 Month 40 : #####
 Month 41 : #####
 Month 42 : #####
 Month 43 : ##
 Month 44 : #####
 Month 45 : #####
 Month 46 : #####
 Month 47 : #####
 Month 48 : #####
 Month 49 : #####
 Month 50 : #####
 Month 51 : #####
 Month 52 : #####
 Month 53 : #####
 Month 54 : #####
 Month 55 : #####
 Month 56 : #####
 Month 57 : #####
 Month 58 : #####
 Month 59 : #####

Age ratio of 6-29 months to 30-59 months: 0.92 (The value should be around 0.85).:
 p-value = 0.167 (as expected)

Statistical evaluation of sex and age ratios (using Chi squared statistic):

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	181/150.8 (1.2)	115/144.3 (0.8)	296/295.1 (1.0)	1.57
18 to 29	12	154/147.0 (1.0)	159/140.7 (1.1)	313/287.7 (1.1)	0.97
30 to 41	12	145/142.5 (1.0)	159/136.4 (1.2)	304/278.9 (1.1)	0.91
42 to 53	12	128/140.3 (0.9)	141/134.2 (1.1)	269/274.5 (1.0)	0.91
54 to 59	6	42/69.4 (0.6)	48/66.4 (0.7)	90/135.8 (0.7)	0.88
6 to 59	54	650/636.0 (1.0)	622/636.0 (1.0)		1.05

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.432 (boys and girls equally represented)
 Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.001 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.002 (significant difference)
 Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)

Digit preference Weight:

Digit .0 : #####
 Digit .1 : #####
 Digit .2 : #####
 Digit .3 : #####
 Digit .4 : #####
 Digit .5 : #####
 Digit .6 : #####
 Digit .7 : #####
 Digit .8 : #####
 Digit .9 : #####

Digit preference score: **7** (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)
 p-value for chi2: 0.000 (significant difference)

Digit preference Height:

Digit .0 : #####
 Digit .1 : #####
 Digit .2 : #####
 Digit .3 : #####
 Digit .4 : #####
 Digit .5 : #####
 Digit .6 : #####
 Digit .7 : #####
 Digit .8 : #####
 Digit .9 : #####

Digit preference score: **7** (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)
 p-value for chi2: 0.000 (significant difference)

Digit preference MUAC:

Digit .0 : #####
 Digit .1 : #####
 Digit .2 : #####
 Digit .3 : #####
 Digit .4 : #####
 Digit .5 : #####
 Digit .6 : #####

Digit .7 : #####
 Digit .8 : #####
 Digit .9 : #####

Digit preference score: 7 (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)
 p-value for chi2: 0.000 (significant difference)

Evaluation of Standard deviation, Normal distribution, Skewness and Kurtosis using the 3 exclusion (Flag) procedures

	no exclusion	exclusion from reference mean (WHO flags)	exclusion from observed mean (SMART flags)
WHZ			
Standard Deviation SD: (The SD should be between 0.8 and 1.2)	1.27	1.27	1.15
Prevalence (< -2) observed:	9.1%	9.1%	8.2%
calculated with current SD:	7.8%	7.8%	6.1%
calculated with a SD of 1:	3.6%	3.6%	3.7%
HAZ			
Standard Deviation SD: (The SD should be between 0.8 and 1.2)	1.91	1.60	1.21
Prevalence (< -2) observed:	52.3%	52.5%	53.2%
calculated with current SD:	47.6%	49.0%	51.4%
calculated with a SD of 1:	45.4%	48.4%	51.7%
WAZ			
Standard Deviation SD: (The SD should be between 0.8 and 1.2)	1.19	1.19	1.11
Prevalence (< -2) observed:	23.7%	23.7%	23.5%
calculated with current SD:	25.4%	25.4%	24.5%
calculated with a SD of 1:	21.5%	21.5%	22.2%

Results for Shapiro-Wilk test for normally (Gaussian) distributed data:
 WHZ p= 0.000 p= 0.000 p= 0.000
 HAZ p= 0.000 p= 0.000 p= 0.000
 WAZ p= 0.002 p= 0.002 p= 0.006
 (If p < 0.05 then the data are not normally distributed. If p > 0.05 you can consider the data normally distributed)

Skewness

WHZ	-0.04	-0.04	-0.12
HAZ	1.84	0.91	0.22
WAZ	0.05	0.05	-0.11

If the value is:
 -below minus 0.4 there is a relative excess of wasted/stunted/underweight subjects in the sample
 -between minus 0.4 and minus 0.2, there may be a relative excess of wasted/stunted/underweight subjects in the sample.
 -between minus 0.2 and plus 0.2, the distribution can be considered as symmetrical.
 -between 0.2 and 0.4, there may be an excess of obese/tall/overweight subjects in the sample.
 -above 0.4, there is an excess of obese/tall/overweight subjects in the sample

Kurtosis

WHZ	0.19	0.19	-0.47
HAZ	7.59	2.54	-0.37
WAZ	0.43	0.43	-0.18

Kurtosis characterizes the relative size of the body versus the tails of the distribution. Positive kurtosis indicates relatively large tails and small body. Negative kurtosis indicates relatively large body and small tails.
 If the absolute value is:
 -above 0.4 it indicates a problem. There might have been a problem with data collection or sampling.
 -between 0.2 and 0.4, the data may be affected with a problem.
 -less than an absolute value of 0.2 the distribution can be considered as normal.

Test if cases are randomly distributed or aggregated over the clusters by calculation of the Index of Dispersion (ID) and comparison with the Poisson distribution for:

WHZ < -2: ID=4.09 (p=0.000)
 WHZ < -3: ID=1.47 (p=0.005)
 Oedema: ID=2.02 (p=0.000)
 GAM: ID=3.89 (p=0.000)
 SAM: ID=1.78 (p=0.000)
 HAZ < -2: ID=1.18 (p=0.130)
 HAZ < -3: ID=1.55 (p=0.001)
 WAZ < -2: ID=2.19 (p=0.000)
 WAZ < -3: ID=1.34 (p=0.027)

Subjects with SMART flags are excluded from this analysis.

The Index of Dispersion (ID) indicates the degree to which the cases are aggregated into certain clusters (the degree to which there are "pockets"). If the ID is less than 1 and p > 0.95 it indicates that the cases are UNIFORMLY distributed among the clusters. If the p value is between 0.05 and 0.95 the cases appear to be randomly distributed among the clusters, if ID is higher than 1 and p is less than 0.05 the cases are aggregated into certain cluster (there appear to be pockets of cases). If this is the case for Oedema but not for WHZ then aggregation of GAM and SAM cases is likely due to inclusion of oedematous cases in GAM and SAM estimates.

Are the data of the same quality at the beginning and the end of the clusters?

Evaluation of the SD for WHZ depending upon the order the cases are measured within each cluster (if one cluster per day is measured then this will be related to the time of the day the measurement is made).

Time point	SD for WHZ															
	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3
01: 1.50 (n=75, f=4)	#####															
02: 1.29 (n=71, f=1)	#####															
03: 1.06 (n=69, f=1)	#####															
04: 1.27 (n=69, f=1)	#####															
05: 1.52 (n=68, f=4)	#####															
06: 1.13 (n=66, f=0)	#####															
07: 1.25 (n=66, f=2)	#####															
08: 1.16 (n=72, f=0)	#####															
09: 1.24 (n=66, f=2)	#####															
10: 1.19 (n=65, f=2)	#####															
11: 1.18 (n=73, f=2)	#####															
12: 1.22 (n=68, f=2)	#####															
13: 1.26 (n=71, f=1)	#####															
14: 1.27 (n=66, f=2)	#####															
15: 1.00 (n=65, f=0)	#####															
16: 1.41 (n=65, f=2)	#####															
17: 1.30 (n=60, f=2)	#####															
18: 1.29 (n=50, f=2)	#####															
19: 1.30 (n=26, f=0)	OOOOOOOOOOOOOOOOOOOO															
20: 1.30 (n=14, f=1)	~~~~~															
21: 1.50 (n=06, f=0)	~~~~~															
22: 1.75 (n=04, f=0)	~~~~~															
23: 1.44 (n=02, f=1)	~~~~~															

(when n is much less than the average number of subjects per cluster different symbols are used: 0 for n < 80% and ~ for n < 40%; The numbers marked "f" are the numbers of SMART flags found in the different time points)

Analysis by Team

Team	A	B	C	D	E	F
n =	228	233	215	175	199	222

Percentage of values flagged with SMART flags:

WHZ:	0.4	6.1	1.9	1.7	5.1	3.7
HAZ:	0.0	3.9	3.3	26.3	2.0	4.1
WAZ:	0.4	2.6	0.9	5.8	1.0	3.7

Age ratio of 6-29 months to 30-59 months:

	0.71	0.86	1.53	1.27	0.67	0.79
--	------	------	------	------	------	------

Sex ratio (male/female):

	0.98	0.97	1.01	1.40	0.84	1.20
--	------	------	------	------	------	------

Digit preference Weight (%):

.0 :	14	27	2	1	1	3
.1 :	7	12	19	8	16	11
.2 :	7	10	22	22	18	13
.3 :	8	8	9	6	15	11
.4 :	14	8	7	18	13	15
.5 :	8	12	3	12	7	9
.6 :	10	6	15	11	10	6
.7 :	10	6	5	5	7	10
.8 :	12	6	5	11	10	9
.9 :	10	5	14	6	6	14
DPS:	8	21	22	20	16	12

Digit preference score (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)

Digit preference Height (%):

.0 :	12	24	8	3	3	2
.1 :	10	6	16	21	11	18
.2 :	12	12	10	15	19	14
.3 :	12	12	7	7	20	14
.4 :	7	9	6	11	18	12
.5 :	15	16	2	21	4	9
.6 :	9	6	14	7	8	8
.7 :	7	6	7	5	9	11
.8 :	7	4	14	8	7	6
.9 :	10	6	15	3	2	8
DPS:	8	19	15	21	22	14

Digit preference score (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)

Digit preference MUAC (%):

.0 :	3	17	10	7	4	5
.1 :	9	6	13	3	15	18
.2 :	13	12	19	9	22	8
.3 :	10	9	8	11	22	10
.4 :	10	10	14	17	8	18
.5 :	13	20	7	13	5	11
.6 :	12	4	4	15	11	8
.7 :	15	8	3	7	6	8
.8 :	11	7	10	11	3	4

.9 : 4 6 13 8 6 11
 DPS: 13 17 15 13 23 15
 Digit preference score (0-7 excellent, 8-12 good, 13-20 acceptable and > 20 problematic)

Standard deviation of WHZ:

SD 0.97 1.23 1.05 1.61 1.32 1.12

Prevalence (< -2) observed:

% 11.8 3.8 30.6 3.5 6.0

Prevalence (< -2) calculated with current SD:

% 11.7 4.2 20.8 3.3 6.9

Prevalence (< -2) calculated with a SD of 1:

% 7.2 3.5 9.4 0.8 4.8

Standard deviation of HAZ:

SD 1.23 1.24 1.24 3.46 1.74 1.44

observed:

% 49.1 61.8 47.9 38.9 57.8 55.4

calculated with current SD:

% 52.9 60.5 42.5 32.1 55.0 54.8

calculated with a SD of 1:

% 53.6 62.9 40.7 5.6 58.7 56.9

Statistical evaluation of sex and age ratios (using Chi squared statistic) for:**Team 1:**

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	18/26.2 (0.7)	15/26.7 (0.6)	33/52.9 (0.6)	1.20
18 to 29	12	34/25.6 (1.3)	28/26.0 (1.1)	62/51.6 (1.2)	1.21
30 to 41	12	27/24.8 (1.1)	31/25.2 (1.2)	58/50.0 (1.2)	0.87
42 to 53	12	25/24.4 (1.0)	27/24.8 (1.1)	52/49.2 (1.1)	0.93
54 to 59	6	9/12.1 (0.7)	14/12.3 (1.1)	23/24.3 (0.9)	0.64
6 to 59	54	113/114.0 (1.0)	115/114.0 (1.0)		0.98

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.895 (boys and girls equally represented)

Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.025 (significant difference)

Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.174 (as expected)

Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.134 (as expected)

Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.009 (significant difference)

Team 2:

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	22/26.7 (0.8)	25/27.4 (0.9)	47/54.1 (0.9)	0.88
18 to 29	12	34/26.0 (1.3)	27/26.7 (1.0)	61/52.7 (1.2)	1.26
30 to 41	12	24/25.2 (1.0)	30/25.9 (1.2)	54/51.1 (1.1)	0.80
42 to 53	12	29/24.8 (1.2)	29/25.5 (1.1)	58/50.3 (1.2)	1.00
54 to 59	6	6/12.3 (0.5)	7/12.6 (0.6)	13/24.9 (0.5)	0.86
6 to 59	54	115/116.5 (1.0)	118/116.5 (1.0)		0.97

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.844 (boys and girls equally represented)
 Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.055 (as expected)
 Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.124 (as expected)
 Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.427 (as expected)
 Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.026 (significant difference)

Team 3:

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	55/25.1 (2.2)	26/24.8 (1.0)	81/49.9 (1.6)	2.12
18 to 29	12	21/24.4 (0.9)	28/24.2 (1.2)	49/48.6 (1.0)	0.75
30 to 41	12	13/23.7 (0.5)	27/23.5 (1.2)	40/47.1 (0.8)	0.48
42 to 53	12	17/23.3 (0.7)	23/23.1 (1.0)	40/46.4 (0.9)	0.74
54 to 59	6	2/11.5 (0.2)	3/11.4 (0.3)	5/22.9 (0.2)	0.67
6 to 59	54	108/107.5 (1.0)	107/107.5 (1.0)		1.01

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.946 (boys and girls equally represented)
 Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.117 (as expected)
 Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)

Team 4:

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	35/23.7 (1.5)	9/16.9 (0.5)	44/40.6 (1.1)	3.89
18 to 29	12	25/23.1 (1.1)	29/16.5 (1.8)	54/39.6 (1.4)	0.86
30 to 41	12	23/22.4 (1.0)	16/16.0 (1.0)	39/38.4 (1.0)	1.44
42 to 53	12	15/22.0 (0.7)	16/15.8 (1.0)	31/37.8 (0.8)	0.94
54 to 59	6	4/10.9 (0.4)	3/7.8 (0.4)	7/18.7 (0.4)	1.33
6 to 59	54	102/87.5 (1.2)	73/87.5 (0.8)		1.40

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.028 (significant excess of boys)
 Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.007 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.016 (significant difference)
 Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.003 (significant difference)
 Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.000 (significant difference)

Team 5:

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	18/21.1 (0.9)	21/25.1 (0.8)	39/46.2 (0.8)	0.86
18 to 29	12	20/20.6 (1.0)	21/24.4 (0.9)	41/45.0 (0.9)	0.95
30 to 41	12	28/20.0 (1.4)	30/23.7 (1.3)	58/43.6 (1.3)	0.93
42 to 53	12	19/19.6 (1.0)	26/23.3 (1.1)	45/42.9 (1.0)	0.73
54 to 59	6	6/9.7 (0.6)	10/11.5 (0.9)	16/21.2 (0.8)	0.60
6 to 59	54	91/99.5 (0.9)	108/99.5 (1.1)		0.84

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

- Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.228 (boys and girls equally represented)
- Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.108 (as expected)
- Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.271 (as expected)
- Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.503 (as expected)
- Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.044 (significant difference)

Team 6:

Age cat.	mo.	boys	girls	total	ratio boys/girls
6 to 17	12	33/28.1 (1.2)	19/23.4 (0.8)	52/51.5 (1.0)	1.74
18 to 29	12	20/27.4 (0.7)	26/22.8 (1.1)	46/50.2 (0.9)	0.77
30 to 41	12	30/26.5 (1.1)	25/22.1 (1.1)	55/48.7 (1.1)	1.20
42 to 53	12	23/26.1 (0.9)	20/21.8 (0.9)	43/47.9 (0.9)	1.15
54 to 59	6	15/12.9 (1.2)	11/10.8 (1.0)	26/23.7 (1.1)	1.36
6 to 59	54	121/111.0 (1.1)	101/111.0 (0.9)		1.20

The data are expressed as observed number/expected number (ratio of obs/expect)

- Overall sex ratio: p-value = 0.179 (boys and girls equally represented)
- Overall age distribution: p-value = 0.753 (as expected)
- Overall age distribution for boys: p-value = 0.405 (as expected)
- Overall age distribution for girls: p-value = 0.774 (as expected)
- Overall sex/age distribution: p-value = 0.099 (as expected)

Evaluation of the SD for WHZ depending upon the order the cases are measured within each cluster (if one cluster per day is measured then this will be related to the time of the day the measurement is made).

Team: 1

Time point	SD for WHZ
01: 1.22 (n=13, f=0)	#####
02: 1.22 (n=12, f=0)	#####
03: 0.77 (n=12, f=0)	#####
04: 1.26 (n=13, f=1)	#####
05: 1.13 (n=13, f=0)	#####
06: 0.63 (n=10, f=0)	#####
07: 1.33 (n=13, f=1)	#####
08: 0.89 (n=13, f=0)	####
09: 0.62 (n=13, f=0)	###
10: 0.87 (n=13, f=0)	###
11: 0.74 (n=12, f=0)	#####
12: 0.97 (n=12, f=0)	##
13: 0.84 (n=13, f=0)	###
14: 0.72 (n=12, f=0)	###
15: 0.80 (n=13, f=0)	###
16: 0.89 (n=12, f=0)	#####
17: 0.73 (n=13, f=0)	~~~~~
18: 1.31 (n=09, f=1)	~~~~~
19: 1.05 (n=04, f=0)	~~~~~
20: 0.86 (n=02, f=0)	~~~~~

(when n is much less than the average number of subjects per cluster different symbols are used: 0 for n < 80% and ~ for n < 40%; The numbers marked "f" are the numbers of SMART flags found in the different time points)

Team: 2

Time point	SD for WHZ
01: 1.46 (n=14, f=1)	#####
02: 0.88 (n=12, f=0)	###
03: 1.07 (n=14, f=0)	#####
04: 1.14 (n=13, f=0)	#####
05: 1.39 (n=13, f=0)	#####
06: 0.77 (n=12, f=0)	
07: 0.63 (n=11, f=0)	
08: 1.02 (n=12, f=0)	#####
09: 1.09 (n=11, f=0)	#####
10: 1.43 (n=12, f=0)	#####
11: 1.02 (n=14, f=0)	#####
12: 1.58 (n=14, f=2)	#####
13: 1.26 (n=14, f=1)	#####
14: 1.62 (n=13, f=1)	#####
15: 1.04 (n=10, f=0)	#####
16: 1.38 (n=11, f=0)	#####
17: 1.54 (n=11, f=1)	#####
18: 1.28 (n=10, f=1)	#####
19: 1.20 (n=03, f=0)	~~~~~

(when n is much less than the average number of subjects per cluster different symbols are used: 0 for n < 80% and ~ for n < 40%; The numbers marked "f" are the numbers of SMART flags found in the different time points)

Team: 3

Time point	SD for WHZ
01: 1.12 (n=11, f=0)	#####
02: 1.05 (n=12, f=0)	#####
03: 0.76 (n=11, f=0)	
04: 1.04 (n=11, f=0)	#####
05: 1.20 (n=12, f=0)	#####
06: 0.87 (n=12, f=0)	###
07: 0.76 (n=11, f=0)	
08: 1.21 (n=10, f=0)	#####
09: 0.86 (n=12, f=0)	###
10: 1.13 (n=12, f=0)	#####
11: 0.93 (n=12, f=0)	#####
12: 1.12 (n=12, f=0)	#####
13: 1.20 (n=12, f=0)	#####
14: 1.00 (n=11, f=0)	#####
15: 0.82 (n=12, f=0)	#
16: 0.94 (n=11, f=0)	#####
17: 1.49 (n=09, f=1)	#####
18: 0.94 (n=10, f=0)	#####
19: 0.95 (n=06, f=0)	OOOOOO
20: 1.90 (n=04, f=1)	~~~~~

(when n is much less than the average number of subjects per cluster different symbols are used: 0 for n < 80% and ~ for n < 40%; The numbers marked "f" are the numbers of SMART flags found in the different time points)

Team: 4

Time point	SD for WHZ
01: 1.68 (n=13, f=1)	#####
02: 1.22 (n=10, f=0)	#####
03: 1.39 (n=10, f=0)	#####
04: 1.84 (n=10, f=1)	#####
05: 1.02 (n=11, f=0)	#####
06: 1.81 (n=10, f=0)	#####
07: 1.88 (n=08, f=0)	#####
08: 1.69 (n=12, f=1)	#####
09: 1.83 (n=09, f=1)	#####
10: 1.21 (n=06, f=0)	OOOOOOOOOOOOOOOO
11: 1.68 (n=10, f=1)	#####
12: 1.30 (n=10, f=0)	#####

Appendix 7: BARAN NGO last three years SAM OPD nutrition activity

Bu Ali Rehabilitation and Aid Network

Kandahar Province

Nutrition Departments

Year :
1393

S/N	Activity	Months												Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1	Total New Admasion	537	627	602	736	661	974	543	836	688	882	614	682	8382
2	Cure	495	507	552	519	585	553	512	628	675	663	769	643	7101
3	Deaths	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3	2	2	1	11
4	Defaults	27	5	33	23	26	26	30	31	36	32	39	31	339
RUTF														
5	Opening Balance	40016	43620	22280	31901	31178	36338	27685	32252	54637	105140	90195	100946	616188
6	Quantity Received	51000	25500	62250	75750	83745	106500	103550	126150	151880	96850	118650	104900	1106725
7	Quantity Used	47396	46840	53129	75973	79914	112383	98783	103765	101377	111795	107899	101222	1040476
8	Closing Balance	43620	22280	31401	31678	35009	30455	32252	54637	105140	90195	100946	104624	682237

Year :
1394

S/N	Activity	Months												Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1	Total New Admasion	866	1003	833	1014	1373	1207	849	971	882	857	734	842	11431

2	Cure	703	598	527	1081	912	928	938	1145	1068	956	799	723	10378
3	Deaths	1	5	0	0	0	1	5	5	3	1	0	2	23
4	Defaults	27	17	14	20	27	26	24	32	35	25	56	47	350
RUTF														
5	Opening Balance	104624	90231	112334	90102	129464	94564	120376	108598	138038	120813	95440	223977	1428561
6	Quantity Received	101250	149550	84300	210450	109200	190647	146294	185237	142500	135750	255019	94868	1805065
7	Quantity Used	115643	127447	106532	171088	144100	164835	158072	155797	159725	161123	126482	153956	1744800
8	Closing Balance	90231	112334	90102	129464	94564	120376	108598	138038	120813	95440	223977	164889	1488826

Year :
1395

S/N	Activity	Months												Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1	Total New Admasion	889	1014	918	872	1524	988	1125						7330
2	Cure	895	690	904	826	920	794	910						5939
3	Deaths	3	1	1	0	1	0	2						8
4	Defaults	40	31	48	44	58	35	104						360
RUTF														
5	Opening Balance	164889	144840	196802	154480	117258	156738	175043						
6	Quantity Received	110250	186450	106500	96000	213900	191250	136500						
7	Quantity Used	134478	134488	148822	133222	174420	172945	154603						
8	Closing Balance	140661	196802	154480	117258	156738	175043	156940	0	0	0	0	0	

Appendix 9: "White Area" handmade Map

Appendix 10: Training Schedule

MSRA –SMART Assessment Kandahar December 2016 Training Schedule

Day	Teachers	Course
161225 Sun	Dr Giorgio Dr Ehsan Dr Ali	Assessment why? Different Kind of Assessment MSRA Kandahar Assessment I-ry and II-ry purposes Assessment methodology – the SMART component Data Quality Data Quantity Errors: Sampling, Bias, Systematic, Rounding, Digit prefer Assessment plan Phase 1 Q&A
161226 Mon	Dr Giorgio Dr Ali Dr Ehsan Dr Ali	Malnutrition and Mortality definitions MSRA Kandahar protocol in detail The Questionnaire, introduction The Questionnaire in detail, step by step Procedures of Anthropometry in Children 6-59mths Q&A Questionnaire 1.0 test, simulation & chronometry Video “How To”: MUAC and WHZ round 1
161227 Tue	Dr Ehsan Dr Giorgio Dr Ali	Review day 1 & 2 EPI SMART- modified household random sampling Briefing Standardization Test:11 children round 1 Standardization Test: 11 children round 2 Debriefing Q&A Questionnaire 2.0 test, role playing & chronometry
161228 Wed	Dr Ali Dr Ehsan Dr Giorgio Dr Ali	Review Standardization Test Briefing Field Tests Sector I (teams A B C) dr Ali (Kulcha Abad) Field Test Sector II (teams D E F) Dr Ehsan (Tamanian) Debriefing Video “How to”: MUAC and WHZ round 2
161229 Thu	Dr Ali Dr Giorgio	Questionnaire 2.6 test Role Playing Simulations and chronometry Review and discussion Field test(s) analysis Q&A
161230 Friday	Rest	Rest
161231 Sun	Dr Giorgio Dr Ehsan + Secu Expert Dr Ali	Course Wrap Up GPS training hands on GIS security analysis: village level Clusters to Teams Teams orders of missions Preparations for day 01: check up lists & random tables Conclusions and thanks

11. Results Phase 1 (anthropometries 1: 993)

11.1 Anthropometric results (based on WHO standards 2006):

Definitions of acute malnutrition should be given (for example, global acute malnutrition is defined as <-2 z scores weight-for-height and/or oedema, severe acute malnutrition is defined as <-3z scores weight-for-height and/or oedema)

Exclusion of z-scores from Observed mean SMART flags: WHZ -3 to 3; HAZ -3 to 3; WAZ -3 to 3

Table 11.1: Distribution of age and sex of sample

AGE (mo)	Boys		Girls		Total		Ratio
	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	Boy:girl
6-17	113	59.8	76	40.2	189	21.2	1.5
18-29	107	47.1	120	52.9	227	25.5	0.9
30-41	104	48.1	112	51.9	216	24.2	0.9
42-53	85	44.3	107	55.7	192	21.5	0.8
54-59	29	43.3	38	56.7	67	7.5	0.8
Total	438	49.2	453	50.8	891	100.0	1.0

Table 11.2: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on weight-for-height z-scores (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 865	Boys n = 426	Girls n = 439
Prevalence of global malnutrition (<-2 z-score and/or oedema)	(72) 8.3 % (5.3 - 12.9 95% C.I.)	(45) 10.6 % (6.3 - 17.3 95% C.I.)	(27) 6.2 % (3.9 - 9.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score, no oedema)	(61) 7.1 % (4.2 - 11.6 95% C.I.)	(36) 8.5 % (4.6 - 15.1 95% C.I.)	(25) 5.7 % (3.5 - 9.2 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (<-3 z-score and/or oedema)	(11) 1.3 % (0.6 - 2.8 95% C.I.)	(9) 2.1 % (0.9 - 5.0 95% C.I.)	(2) 0.5 % (0.1 - 1.8 95% C.I.)

The prevalence of oedema is 1.0 %

Table 11.3: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on weight-for-height z-scores and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate wasting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	182	0	0.0	24	13.2	155	85.2	3	1.6
18-29	217	1	0.5	16	7.4	195	89.9	5	2.3
30-41	209	0	0.0	12	5.7	196	93.8	1	0.5
42-53	190	0	0.0	7	3.7	183	96.3	0	0.0
54-59	67	1	1.5	2	3.0	64	95.5	0	0.0
Total	865	2	0.2	61	7.1	793	91.7	9	1.0

Table 11.4: Distribution of acute malnutrition and oedema based on weight-for-height z-scores

	<-3 z-score	>=-3 z-score
Oedema present	Marasmic kwashiorkor No. 1 (0.1 %)	Kwashiorkor No. 8 (0.9 %)
Oedema absent	Marasmic No. 13 (1.5 %)	Not severely malnourished No. 864 (97.5 %)

Table 11.5: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on MUAC cut off's (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 887	Boys n = 435	Girls n = 452
Prevalence of global malnutrition (< 125 mm and/or oedema)	(122) 13.8 % (10.8 - 17.4 95% C.I.)	(59) 13.6 % (10.0 - 18.1 95% C.I.)	(63) 13.9 % (10.2 - 18.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (< 125 mm and >= 115 mm, no oedema)	(90) 10.1 % (7.6 - 13.4 95% C.I.)	(42) 9.7 % (6.6 - 14.0 95% C.I.)	(48) 10.6 % (7.3 - 15.2 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (< 115 mm and/or oedema)	(32) 3.6 % (2.4 - 5.4 95% C.I.)	(17) 3.9 % (2.3 - 6.7 95% C.I.)	(15) 3.3 % (1.9 - 5.7 95% C.I.)

Table 11.6: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on MUAC cut off's and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (< 115 mm)		Moderate wasting (>= 115 mm and < 125 mm)		Normal (> = 125 mm)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	189	13	6.9	49	25.9	127	67.2	3	1.6
18-29	226	6	2.7	31	13.7	189	83.6	5	2.2
30-41	214	1	0.5	6	2.8	207	96.7	1	0.5
42-53	191	4	2.1	2	1.0	185	96.9	0	0.0
54-59	67	0	0.0	3	4.5	64	95.5	0	0.0
Total	887	24	2.7	91	10.3	772	87.0	9	1.0

Table.11.7: Prevalence of underweight based on weight-for-age z-scores by sex

	All n = 871	Boys n = 424	Girls n = 447
Prevalence of underweight (<-2 z-score)	(202) 23.2 % (18.8 - 28.3 95% C.I.)	(112) 26.4 % (21.2 - 32.4 95% C.I.)	(90) 20.1 % (15.1 - 26.3 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate underweight (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(140) 16.1 % (12.9 - 19.8 95% C.I.)	(78) 18.4 % (14.5 - 23.1 95% C.I.)	(62) 13.9 % (10.1 - 18.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe underweight (<-3 z-score)	(62) 7.1 % (5.1 - 9.8 95% C.I.)	(34) 8.0 % (5.2 - 12.1 95% C.I.)	(28) 6.3 % (4.1 - 9.5 95% C.I.)

Table 11.8: Prevalence of underweight by age, based on weight-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe underweight (<-3 z-score)		Moderate underweight (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	184	18	9.8	24	13.0	142	77.2	3	1.6
18-29	216	17	7.9	39	18.1	160	74.1	5	2.3
30-41	213	18	8.5	35	16.4	160	75.1	1	0.5
42-53	192	4	2.1	30	15.6	158	82.3	0	0.0
54-59	66	5	7.6	12	18.2	49	74.2	0	0.0
Total	871	62	7.1	140	16.1	669	76.8	9	1.0

Table 11.9: Prevalence of stunting based on height-for-age z-scores and by sex

	All n = 841	Boys n = 407	Girls n = 434
Prevalence of stunting (<-2 z-score)	(456) 54.2 % (49.8 - 58.6 95% C.I.)	(216) 53.1 % (48.1 - 58.0 95% C.I.)	(240) 55.3 % (48.5 - 61.9 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate stunting (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(248) 29.5 % (25.9 - 33.3 95% C.I.)	(116) 28.5 % (24.3 - 33.2 95% C.I.)	(132) 30.4 % (25.7 - 35.6 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe stunting (<-3 z-score)	(208) 24.7 % (20.5 - 29.5 95% C.I.)	(100) 24.6 % (19.6 - 30.3 95% C.I.)	(108) 24.9 % (19.8 - 30.8 95% C.I.)

Table 11.10: Prevalence of stunting by age based on height-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe stunting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate stunting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	176	17	9.7	35	19.9	124	70.5
18-29	210	56	26.7	70	33.3	84	40.0
30-41	203	72	35.5	71	35.0	60	29.6
42-53	186	46	24.7	55	29.6	85	45.7
54-59	66	17	25.8	17	25.8	32	48.5
Total	841	208	24.7	248	29.5	385	45.8

Table 11.11: Prevalence of overweight based on weight for height cut off's and by sex (no oedema)

	All n = 865	Boys n = 426	Girls n = 439
Prevalence of overweight (WHZ > 2)	(23) 2.7 % (1.7 - 4.1 95% C.I.)	(13) 3.1 % (1.8 - 5.3 95% C.I.)	(10) 2.3 % (1.2 - 4.3 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe overweight (WHZ > 3)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)

Table 11.12: Prevalence of overweight by age, based on weight for height (no oedema)

Age (mo)	Total no.	Overweight (WHZ > 2)		Severe Overweight (WHZ > 3)	
		No.	%	No.	%
6-17	182	1	0.5	0	0.0
18-29	217	4	1.8	0	0.0
30-41	209	6	2.9	0	0.0
42-53	190	9	4.7	0	0.0
54-59	67	3	4.5	0	0.0
Total	865	23	2.7	0	0.0

Table 11.13: Mean z-scores, Design Effects and excluded subjects

Indicator	n	Mean z-scores \pm SD	Design Effect (z-score < -2)	z-scores not available*	z-scores out of range
Weight-for-Height	856	-0.11 \pm 1.17	4.15	14	21
Weight-for-Age	871	-1.24 \pm 1.09	2.72	14	6
Height-for-Age	841	-2.13 \pm 1.23	1.64	0	50

* contains for WHZ and WAZ the children with edema.

Appendix 12. List of villages and randomized Clusters

Geographical unit F1	Population size	Cluster
Amarat	1204	
Bilandai	2370	
Chaplanai	3240	
Deh Ghulaman	1190	
Deh Rajab	2439	
Arazi	1176	
Gurgan	1050	
Kalantar	2450	
Kohkaran	1496	
Khan Agha Qalacha	2100	
Kakarano Goush Khana	1330	1
Loy Karizak	1100	
Loy Bala Karz	2970	
Mansor Ghundi	1855	
Nakodak	2401	
Rambasi	1360	
Rawanai	3500	
Rooh Abad	2310	
Sabzikar	1750	
Soof	1582	
Zakar Sharif	10000	2
Angoriyaan	2100	
Atta Muhammad Khan Kalai	742	
Baldai	1400	
Badizai	581	
Bakhtyar	1330	
Deh Bagh	1890	
Haqdad Kariz	700	
Abdul Rahman Kalai	1064	
Khwaja Ali Baba	2100	
Kochenai Bala Karz	2100	
Khulchabad	2520	
Mard Kala	2450	
Mushkizai	2100	
Mian Joy	700	
Miro Gul	840	
Mula Nazar Kalai	665	
Munara	672	
Nawi Mashor	1568	
Naw Deh	1652	3
Sediqullah Qalacha	2339	
Shafa	910	

Sheer Surkh	2485	
Speen Ziarat	980	
Timorian	2100	
Atmanzi	490	
Walakan	700	
Yakh Kariz	2100	
Zor Mashoor	875	
Gosh Khana	980	
Asia Chap	1343	
Balochano Qalacha	875	
Dehrawood Qalacha	1064	
Deh Khatai	2177	
Deh Kochai	1099	
Ismail Qalacha	2800	
Ghani qalacha	700	
Ghondi QalachaTimorian	700	
Ghundi Bala Karz	1260	
Gundigan	1400	4
Agha Jan Kariz	938	
Hashim Qalacha	1400	
Haji Arab	1750	
Karam Qalacha	1400	
Kariz	2100	
Khonchezai	525	
Kobai	2835	
Masizai	700	
Murghan	2149	
Mat Mala	1050	
Qasam Pul	868	
Sra Kala	1085	
Sari khod Qalacha	784	
Popalzo Qalacha	875	
Tazo Ko Qalacha	840	
Nasaran	420	
Nawi Kalai	1540	
Obaidullah Qalacha	777	
Gul Akhound Zada Qalacha	1032	
Sahibdad Ghandi	1050	
Piro Qalacha	2100	
Beloo Qalacha	1148	
Ghulam Dastageer Qalacha	1932	5
Nazar Muhammad Khan Kariz	1935	
Sra Ghoundi	1113	
Haji Khudia Nazar Qalacha	455	
Nawi Qalacha	476	

Kaghanak	350	
Mazar Kalai	311	
Kshata Kohkaran	2450	
Haji Kotawal	658	
Jamrani	666	
Keshani	700	
Deh Masos	420	
Niko Kariz	560	
Pir Paimal	1071	
Abdul Qudos Kariz	420	
Achackzo Qalacha	1008	
Ibrahim Khalifa Baba	900	
Chahar Bagh	840	
Zoor Kalai	2100	
Etehad Kalai	2100	
Abdul Salam Qalacha	2219	
Mirza Mohammad Khan Qalacha	2100	
Haji Naim Kalai	3000	
Nasrullah Qalacha	735	
Ganj Qalacha	735	6
Sar Mian Joy	840	
Haji Mohamamd Rasool Khan Qalacha	819	
Lala Ghani Qalacha	1043	
Chahardiwal	2100	
Raz Mohammad Qalacha	1400	
Abdul Razeeq Qalacha	490	
Panjab Ghara	1792	
Sheely Main Joy	700	
Dagai	1400	
Ghazi Kalai	2100	
Mulla Nida Mohammad Qalacha	1050	
Kochni Atifaq Mina	840	
Loya etifaq meena	2310	
Faizullah Qalacha	700	
Haji Abdul Qayoom Qalacha	2100	
Sadat Qalacha	1400	
Saloo Khan Chaman	1400	
Lakhshak	1330	
Chaman Kalai	1253	
Haji Baba Qalacha	2100	
Mohammad Gull Qalacha	2205	RC
Regi Qalacha	2170	
Pashtoon Bagh	2015	
Shinghazi Ashabi	2450	
Kochni Char Bagh	770	

Abdul Rashid Khan Qalacha	1260	
Naim Sha	676	
Sharo Kalai	655	
Hajji Omar Jan	430	
Malai Kalai	494	
Hajji Joma Khan	1164	
Esmail Khowaja Mohammad	654	
Nawee Monara	701	
New Etilaq	1771	
Shahid Hajji Bacha Kalai	444	
Kaka Kalai	1096	
Nawee Jailani	395	
Suliman Zai	1400	
Sra Qala	1080	
Maduzi	1360	
Pungi	1700	
Murghan Kecha	1500	
Nawi Deh	1500	
Dai Kalai	1366	7
Laly Kalai	2072	
Jakaan Kalai	579	
Manja	1386	
Kakarano Rabat	1210	
Azam Kala	893	
Braj Kalai	1603	
Sahib Zada Qalacha	1341	
Ghaibe Qalacha	1050	
Mommand	3458	
Popalzo Qalacha	1200	
Awal Khoshab	1200	
Dwaham Khoshab	1000	
Da Ghara Kalai	5250	
Shour Andam	3500	
Mandisar	3510	8
Qazi Kariz	1281	
Karim Kariz	500	
Ghulam Nabi Qalacha	1034	
Haji Muhammad Zai	515	
Abdul Baqi Qalacha	900	
Akhtar Mohd Qalacha	584	
Najoi	1458	
Syed Latif Qalacha	445	
Ubaidullah Qalacha	466	
Mula Abdullah	2240	
Tajo Mama	378	

Haji Sardar	672	
Fazal Qalacha	500	
Sayed Jan Kalai	892	
Keshta Kalai	1351	
Manda Kalai	393	
Enzargai	455	
Ghani Qalacha	860	
Saleh Jan Kalai	357	
Haji Musa Qalacha	1113	
Sayed Jalal Kalai	413	
Jarchi Kalai	877	
Khair Jan Kalai	600	
Haji Ghulam Shah Kalai	900	
Hakeem Jan	1324	
Sardar Kalai	375	
Mohammad Rafiq Qalacha	455	
Hejran Karez	456	
Charband Kariz	279	
Hassan Zai Kalai	1240	
Nahr-e-Rabat	518	
Haji Hanifya	490	
Naqilin Kalai	705	
Zaker Abad	1056	9
Mohammad Shah	1400	
Amir Lalai Kalai	1050	
Haji Aziz	2100	
Ansari	1800	
Etifaq Kalai	1750	
Ansari Mina	980	
Pitaway Kalai	1428	
Tarwakai	641	
Toba	1551	
Yar Dad	690	
Baghtoo	1066	
Khairtot	2445	
Shah Karaiz	734	
Zangitan	1562	
Loy Karaiz	1307	
Abdul Razaq	892	
De Pal	1400	
Arhad	1294	
Khair Para	589	
Mashano Wale	864	
Wali	2427	10
Bagh Deh Sara	1931	

Qondalan	2364	
Sarkhobid	3100	
Hajy Mir Ahmad	886	
Panga	1336	
Kightoo	560	
Kandalan	780	
Behbod Khail	180	
Mir Hamza Khan	660	
Sahebzada	1328	
Wach Baghto	919	
Podina	842	
Zangtan	770	
Ailbak	998	
Awrdo Kas	449	
Siaband	800	
Zartala	1458	
Asikzai Kas	470	
Khodaidad Khail	480	
Albak Suliman Khel	2248	
Pai Nawa Chinar too	336	
Jalol Zai	764	
Khirnai	3090	
Shada	1184	11
Pada Aw Tangai	1449	
Chinaar	2053	
De Karwai Painwa	776	
Chaghni Baghto	1680	
Kala	1746	
Nawa Wayan	419	
Kochnai Karez	1983	
Sha Agha	1611	
Marai Karez	1883	
Darbazan	2124	
Chaghak	1400	
Dizanto	630	
Tapa Lokh	500	
Pacha Kalai	1400	
Sayed Khan	1400	
Zor Kali	1452	
Hasanzai	1505	
Karwai babarn	800	
Dadgi	650	
Fairoja	804	
Mala Sar Tor	905	
Sozanai Asikzai	830	12

Togharq	1462	
Mulawai kariz	800	
Sia Waba	670	
Lal Jan	630	
Khak Sharin	763	
Bora Gana	680	
Maqur	800	
Sya Kol	560	
Ahmad Wila	711	
Pacha Agha Kariz	420	
Saheeb Jan Kalai	2348	
Tanabcha	730	
Zanto Paynawa	630	
Loy Kalai	2690	
Dimo Shak	1984	
Gull Agha Kalai	2216	
Loy Diba	1774	
Loy Mazar	1470	
Tatarin	1176	
Spin Kala	2025	
Sabzal	600	
Sarwar Jan Kala	990	
Hajji Shadi Khan	843	
Hajji Payoo Aka Kalai	1349	13
Shin Gazh	569	
Delak	875	
Pir Mohammad	1149	
Nika Shila	1036	
Abdul Qadus		
Malak Piro Jan		
Lado Kariz		
Lal Khan Kas		
Deh Sabzi	1235	
Kohak	1832	
Hadirah	2240	
Khaleshak	1200	
Mansor Abad	1400	
Mian Joy	1050	
Dorahe Kalai	790	
Chan Gull	2000	
Surkh Chala	2940	
Kheshki	2600	
Loya Munarah	1975	
Mohammad Noor Qalacha	1000	
Loy Tabin	1452	

Khwaja Malk	2472	14
Hajiano Qala	1240	
Babar Kalai	688	
Shoheen Wasat	1680	
Shoheen Suffla	1270	
Shoheen Ulya	1100	
Shahtory Khana Gardab	600	
Sarda Ulya	1100	
Nawi Mazrah	2500	
Wakeel Kala	2195	
Ali Kalai	800	
Jaza	910	
Khosraw Ulya	1435	
Khosraw Sufla	1983	
Joe Lahor	3000	
Chahar Qulba Ulia	1120	
Bala Tabin	1575	
Kochni Munara	1260	
Ghundi Nagahan	2256	
Kocha Nagahan	1300	15
Sami Qalacha	740	
Chahar Qulba-e-Sufla	896	
Najaff Qala	845	
Ba Ba Sahib Langar	1000	
Mazra Abbas	1000	
Gul Qalacha	1170	
Sarday Sufla	400	
Maranjan	3955	
Muhammad Yaqoob Qalacha	800	
Delawar Khan Qalacha	1080	
Saidano Qalacha	500	
Nahar Rawza	1880	
Haji Abdul Hamid Qalacha	526	
Sheer Ahmad	468	
Faqeeran	448	
Shah Ho Karez	840	
Gurji kariz	735	
Wahedian	1178	
Arhad Kalai	1750	
Sarkary Bagh	175	
Fitawi Nagahan	1260	
Habibullah Qalacha	770	
Kshata Surkhchala	1911	
Hanjaran Kalai	700	
Durahi Nawi Kalai	700	

Sayeed Abad Kalai	840	
Dasht Masjed	1400	16
Keshita Joy Lahor	2233	
Jalga	2240	
Nawi Habibullah Qalacha	2324	
Haji Isaq Zai Kalai	2254	
Mraryan	1881	
Mirab Khoran	1777	
Said Mohammad Qalacha	1036	
Palizo	1323	
Shawali Khan Qalacha	1517	
Arman Dag	1818	
Pir Zada	840	
Hasan Abad	700	
Khaish Khalak	700	
Kandak	700	
Aziz Abad	1450	
Muhamad Musa	1750	
Noor Abad	1050	
Dawlat Abad	700	
Safozai Kalai	2100	17
Mazra	2050	
Chahil Gazai	400	
Nasoo	350	
Makoo	490	
Awal Landai Kariz	560	
Naw Abad	350	
Shakoor Kariz	350	
Akhondzada Kariz	490	
Ainak	430	
Samand	688	
Haji Raz Mohammad Kalai	1980	
Lowar Sohbat	574	
Azim Jan Kariz	1830	
Shahi Kariz	920	
Sher Abad	500	
Kshata Sohbat	230	
Mirabkhor	790	
Muslim Abad	2100	
Mandozai	1570	
Hotel Kalai	1950	
Ishq Abad	829	
Sarwar Kariz	325	
Asoda Kariz	625	
Gach Kariz	1220	

Biabanak	930	
Qanat Din Mohammad Kariz	605	
Badizai	511	
Mansoor Kariz	620	
Mohammad Khil	1750	
Shir Mohammad Kariz	455	
Baizai Kalai	560	
Kariz Wal	1050	18
Toor Nika Kalai	455	
Kakarano Kalai	490	
Sayedano Kalai	490	
Babai Kariz	560	
Achikzai Kalai	420	
Shah Zarif Kariz	490	
Shal Ghamai	2100	
Nahre Mir Afzal	700	
Tora Gara	1680	
Khig	490	
Nokar Khill	1190	
Haji Khill Kalai	1190	
Osman Khail	2100	
Doka Kalai	1050	
Haji Taj Mohammad	455	
Haji Muhammad Gul Kalai	655	
China	2100	
Lower Now Abad	1050	
Nizara	420	
Si Totak Kariz	598	
Da Chashami Kariz	524	
Pay Karez	557	
Mali Khail	1202	
Khak Chopan	676	
Qanat Akhter Mohammad Kariz	220	
Dab Samizai	659	
Hotel Nawi Kalai	1304	
Da Jamalzo Wiala	293	
Hamid Kariz	533	
Gull Talab Kariz	496	
Landai Kariz	435	
Da Spin Manda Ghara	507	
Zor Bazar Kalai	1041	
Da Qalachai Kalai	656	19
Said Mohammad Kariz	582	
Hajji Omar Kalai	507	
Sha Gasi Kala	872	

Nahri Jalal Kalai	717	
Lwara Mazra	2075	
Hajji Joma Khan Kalai	784	
Talkhakai Kalai	692	
Qanat Taj Mohammad	471	
Jamalzo Kasa	267	
Changai Kalai	475	
Pada	445	
Da Korai Kariz	993	
Khoshka Barakzai	1251	
Da Morchai Kalai	910	
Baba Ali	500	
Khoshk Kariz	333	
Haibat Kariz	342	
Sarkari Musjed	554	
Nawar Kariz	802	
Lwar Mohammad Masi	624	
Asti Khail	885	
Ebrahim Nika Kariz	647	
Sor Baghal Joma Khan Musjed	335	
Lala Zai	1583	
Spin Kalai	990	
Kamozai Kalai	1113	
Nowrozai Kalai	1317	
Landai Kariz	1059	
Nabo Kariz	761	
Ango Kariz	914	
Pain Kila	1966	
Gardai Kariz	461	
Qazi Kariz	583	
Hayatullah Kalai	1011	20
Qaid Azim Kariz	478	
Hajji Samal Kariz	295	
New Abad Kariz	490	
Kalatka	1170	
Shir Ali Kariz	642	
Afghani Kariz	1143	
Gardai Kosi Kalai	499	
Kochnai China	584	
Haido Kariz	512	
Maywand Chashma	927	
Zangistan	890	
Anjorak Kariz	390	
Lwar Shaghasi	1972	
Khakrizwal Kalai	340	

Yasin Kariz	507	
Da Qabad Kalai	2683	
Said Mohammad Ahga Ziarat	436	
Abdul Karim	229	
Hajji Akhter Mohammad Kariz	1406	
Kako Wiala	229	
Akhtarai Kariz	1105	
Hajji Amanullah Kariz	359	
Hajji Mullah Mohammad Akhond Kalai	1170	
Kochnai China	607	
Nika Baba Kariz	374	
Mohammad Karim Kariz	541	
Wazir Mohammad Kariz	930	
Khiaband	290	
Gull Mohammad Nika Kariz	435	
Shkhanzai	686	
Zarikhar	484	
Jama Kalai	433	
Zardalo Kariz	623	
Tabsakhar Kariz	321	
Hajji Rahmatullah Khan Kariz	230	
Ahmad Khan Kariz	519	
Shokrulla Kariz	247	
Tolak Kariz	451	
Balosano Kalai	307	
China Khir Mohammad Kariz	407	
Mohammad Sha Aka Da Barmo Kalai	701	
Now Abad Kariz	412	
Fida Mohammad Kariz	700	21
Gorgain Kariz	903	
Barakzo Kalai	289	
Qanat Tarakai Kariz	373	
Sor Kariz	244	
Mashk Kariz	924	
Mir Hotak Kariz	604	
Chol Abak Kariz	356	
Kochnai Kariz	561	
Choghakai Kalai	1240	
Da Atak Kariz	379	
Norzo Kalai	579	
Mullah Agha Jan Kalai	1346	
Chokarai Kalai	937	
Da Tarai Kariz	925	
China Mohammad Rasool Khan	376	
Sopi Karim Kariz	239	

Azim Kariz	478	
Da Warzo Kochnai Kariz	278	
Nadi Kalai	1113	
Khankhail Kariz	815	
Gorgano Kalai	366	
Hajji Mohammad Kalai	493	
Mohammad Hassan Kalai	360	
Spin Kariz	874	
Lalazai Band Timor	575	
Mali Khail Kariz	816	
Mandabad Kariz	1126	
Bolagh Kariz	718	
Mia Kariz	896	
Baridad Kariz	898	
Sagai Kariz	492	
Babaran Chashma Mohammad Khan	406	
Nazar Mohammad Kariz	362	
Traiw Kariz	520	
Mohammad Wais Kariz	275	
Qanat Fati Khan	2346	
Abil Kalai	389	
Allaudin Kariz	311	
Hajji Honar Kasa	257	
Malak Khoday Dad Kariz	884	
Rafat Ali Kalai	412	
Qanat Bostan	385	
Da Zarai Walaswali Kalai	770	22
Kandai Khail Kalai	692	
Khan Jan Nika Kalai	809	
Maywand Kariz	454	
Sadiq Sha Baba Kariz	1381	
Raigai	1157	
Now Wialai Kalai	1403	
Qalai Shamer China	826	
Kochnai Zangla Karez	1232	
Nawar Kalai Chashmai	1129	
Shahwani Kariz	509	
Mama Kariz	431	
Jogram	1003	
Madrasa Kalai	349	
Dabak	778	
Joy Mohmmand	1391	
Toor Manda Ghari Kalai	835	
Rangrizan	542	
Khalifa Qasab Kalai	882	

Abdul Azim Kalai	1470	
Khalifa Abdul Mohammad Kalai	1260	
Haji Aslam Jan Agha Kalai	1785	
Bazar Juma Kalai	1428	
Baloch Qasab Kalai	1170	
Haji Ghafar Shah Agha	973	
Haji Pacha Khan Kalai	924	
Badwan Kalai	702	
Armar Kalai	1050	
Mohammadzai kalai	770	
Bal Ghour Abdul Mohammad	917	23
Malik Ahmad Kalai	1338	
Baresan	1260	
Haji Obidullah Kalai	1876	
Haji Agha Lalai Kalai	1652	
Haji Kablai	1106	
Haji Abdul Kala	1512	
Haji Sayed Mohammed Kalai	1113	
Haji Bahaudin Kalai	2100	
Haji Khair Mohammed	2100	
Haji Mohammad Afzal Kalai	1800	
Haji Habibullah Kalai	1620	
Haji Gul Mohammad kalai	1800	
Haji Paynda Mohamad Kalai	2270	
Haji Abdul Baqi	2100	
Haji Faiz Mohammed Kalai	1100	
Haji Abdul Wadood Kalai	2030	
Gul Agha Kalai	1855	24
Nowrozi	1770	
Now Rozi Kochian Kalai	1225	
Fatlah Kala	2093	
Ibrahim Zo Kalai	2030	
Haji Mohammed Shafi Kalai	2079	
Haji Khairullah Kalai	2065	
Naik Mohammed Kalai	2086	
Chilghoor Haji Kubali	2065	
Lowy Kalai	1552	
Kochnai Kalai	1681	
Faizo Kalai	1684	
Kalacha	1351	
Chaman	1012	
Shikh Qalandar	317	
Dabak	418	
Tokal	632	
Hajji Nanai Agha	1181	

Shin Ghazai	950	
Mahee	132	
Tajdar	821	25
Sahib Jan	794	
Balada	612	
Salih Khan	488	
Hajji Gull Mohammad Agha	1212	
Nawroz	676	
Hajji Abdul Rahman	1205	
Hajji Salam Khan	221	
Hajji Daro Khan	669	
Shinkai	503	
Hajji Malang	1362	
Da Saidano Kalai	961	
Hajji Khan Mohammad	219	
Toorak Kalai	484	
Mohammad Ewaz Kalai	451	
Kochnai Qala	664	
Samizo Kalai	473	
Panjpayee	1357	
Hajji Agha Lalai	1435	
Hajji Gul Mohammad Khan	1167	
Hajji Mamak	1616	
Malak Raz Mohammad	820	
Abdul Qadim Lala	1219	
Dasht Kalai	588	
Lowy Musjad	1341	
Qatar Kalai	1417	
Kakarano Kalai	1482	
Da Khanano Kalai	1009	
Khair Mohammad "Haydari"	1257	
Mohammad Bayan Aka	1540	
Abdul Ghani	2139	26
Sultanzo	558	
Mohammad Rashid	1732	
Din Mohammad	277	
Hajji Baghwan	1454	
Koshkak	245	
Mullah Abdul Shakoor	327	
Abdul Rahim	1761	
Hajji Mohammad Noor	1484	
Hajji Mohammadulla	572	
Hajji Nik Mohammad	261	
Said Ahmad	342	
Hajji Obidullah	708	

Hajji Abdullah	194	
Mullah Ahmad	475	
Malim Gholam Nabi	745	
Nayab Khail	697	
Nahri Pati Khan	638	
Zanzair Bor Mohammad	177	
Da Ghra Kalai	699	
Kochnai Nacharai	362	
Lalo Mama	564	
Hajji Mohammad Esmail	156	
Hajji Gholam Sarwar Aka	1105	
Hajji Mohammad Yar Aka	1046	
Mahajerin	723	
Hajji Loy Agha	1823	
Hajji Mahiuldin	833	
Malak Agha	595	
Da Karizo Loy Musjed	514	
Hajji Fazal Mohammad	465	
Nizamuldin	896	
Khoday Dad	551	
Amanullah	388	
Akhondzada Khail	434	
Bazar	406	
Malim Sahib Mohammad Naim	254	
Hajji Saifullah	164	
Hajji Mohammad Gul	227	
Hajji Mullah Tahir Akhond	696	
Hajji Amanullah	1316	27
Hajji Haya Mohammad	1428	
Abdul Halim	815	
Marjan	305	
Abdul Hakim	1352	
Fida Mohammad	609	
Agha Gull	646	
Gholam Haydar	1504	
Abdul Raziq	999	
Shamshir	256	
Abdul Samad	353	
Adamzoi	1186	
Malak Abdul Rashid	1005	
Fida Mohammad	1110	
Hajji Mohammad Yar	1202	
Abdul Jalil	1250	
Niaz Mohammad	284	
Hajji Faizullah	520	

Doctor Mohammad Naim	746	
Hajji Wali Mohammad	368	
Hajji Malim Sahib	786	
Hajji Abdul Ghapor	419	
Mohammad Anwar	190	
Mamor Haqnazar	687	
Hajji Dust Mohammad	269	
Hajji Gholam	458	
Hajji Nik Nazar	639	
Hajji Yar Mohammad	199	
Rahimdad	529	
Hajji Abdul Rahim	423	
Abdul Hadi	629	
Amanullah	679	
Hajji Mohammad Alim	256	
Hajji Rahmatullah	142	
Hajji Ata Jan	360	
Haq Dad	202	
Mullah Shabozai	550	
Hajji Janan	671	
Habiburahman	672	
Hajji Mohammad Qasam Agha	162	
Hajji Mohammad Anwer	1278	
Loy Lala	276	
Biabanak	1163	
Hajji Baridad	1054	RC
Hajji Sultan Massod Sha	1246	
Hajji Mohammad Haq	334	
Hajji Mohammad Ali	406	
Yar Mohammad	532	
Hajji Mohammad Karim Dad	878	
Hajji Sat Mohammad	391	
Hajji Abdullah Jan	228	
Haji Abdul Rashid	419	
Mullah Gulistan	177	
Loy Saidan	1332	
Haidar Shah	287	
Salor Yaran	530	
Nasrudin Khan	979	
Mohammad Qasam	996	
Fail Salam	1202	
Lal Mohammad	906	
Abdul Qayoom	1362	
Abdul Kafi	751	
Hajji Baran Khan	1538	

Hajji Ata Jan	1547	
Mohammad Ayob	781	
Mohammad Akram	526	
Gholam Sakhi	574	
Said Yasin Agha	1459	
Gull Mohammad	1337	
Abdul Raur	1364	
Kasi Agha Lalai	295	
Abdul Habib	323	
Abdul Qados	740	
Abdul Razaq	664	
Malim Musa Jan	355	
Shin Ghazai	353	
Malim Musa	416	
Ahmad Sha	817	
Mohammad Ghaws	291	
Said Mohammad	513	
Madina	941	28
Abdul Jalal Khan	1655	
Abdul Sami	935	
Khaybar Hajji Shirin	506	
Hajji Mohammad Zai	1426	
Hajji Baye Khan	1543	
Hajji Mohammad Sha	1508	
Malik Murtaza Kalai	2100	
Haji Fida Mohammed	2100	
Haj Ghulam Mohammed	2100	
Haji Dadullah	1190	
Abdul Jabar Awal	574	
Haji Mohammed Rafiq	560	
Adozi Kalai	735	
Haji Abdul Jabar 2	2100	
Mohammed Azim Jan Kalai	588	
Haji Ashraf Khan	2100	
Zara Jama	1974	
Haji Wali Jan Masjed	2072	
Shaheed Mahal	1295	
Haji Gud Kalai	875	29
Haji Zarif	420	
Shadizi Kalai	812	
Ahmadia Jama	1925	
Haji Dadullah Masjed 2	1911	
Haji Toor Masjed	798	
Haji Lalai	1379	
Hajji Abdul Razaq Pump	1099	

Fashtun Abad	1466	
Mawlawi Mohammad Azim	1948	
Bahador Zai	2163	
Gowad Hajji Abdul Haq	1731	
Potai Mirhamza (Miralzai)	1722	
Gholam Hayuldin	1228	
Hajji Jajan Da Kalai Shora	2014	
Mulla Abdul Razaq	1471	
Toor Qari	1448	
Markaz Sahib Jan	1246	
Hajji Mohammad Gull	1414	
Hazrat Bilal	2198	30
Hajji Bakht Mohammad	1829	
Sona Wali Abdul Khaliq	2170	
Hajji Toor Gull	1339	
Hajji Abdul Karim Khan	2188	
Hajji Fati Khan Kalai	325	
Lwar Kablian	853	
Sarkatib Salam	2119	
Qasaban	1456	
Elahi Jama	1657	
Hajji Jalat	2066	
Hajji Abdul Khaliq	1136	
Shir Mohammad	1190	
Sarfraz Khan	910	
Haji Mohammad Azim Kalai	1925	
Hajji Satar	1437	
Hajji Said Mohammad	1155	
Hajji Eshaqzai Aka Khail	2017	
Sahib Jan	1488	31
Haji Mohammad Nabi	2254	
??Garandai	1626	
Mohammad Zahir	1781	
Saifuddin	2338	
Marufian	1841	
Hajji Barakzai	812	
Hajji Mola Amir Mohammad	1491	
Hajji Said Rahim Agha	1925	
Mulla Darya Khan	1925	
Mawlawi Noor Mohammad	2222	
Malim Mohammad Dawod	2375	
Haji Sahib Khan	1715	
Hajji Mohammad Alam	1360	
Mullawi Hanif Ishaqzai	2625	
Popalzo Kalai	1225	

Barakzo Kalai	1281	32
Mawlla Dad Kamision Manda	1666	
Hajji Abdul Ahad	686	
Hajji Abdul Hakim	1785	
Hajji Wali Sha	2359	
Akhtar Jan	2674	
Abdul Razaq Kalai	1015	
Lalai	1870	
Salim	2624	
Eshaq Zai	2054	
Haji Salih Mahmmd Pahlwan	2286	
Hajji Bismillah	1502	
Hajji Abdul Karim & Lali	1442	
Qumandan Mohammad Lal	819	
Mullah Manan	1891	
Mallak Abdul Kabir	1190	
Haji Mohammad Mosa	2198	33
Shahin	1820	
H. Abidullah Barakzai	1855	
Malik Abdul Samad	2037	
Haji Ghawsadin	2100	
Shin Gull	1362	
Malak Akhter Mohammad	1190	
Hajji Sarwar	1890	
Hajji Wali Jan	1631	
Eshaq Zai & Hajji Mohammad	1700	
Hajji Wali Jan Kharoti	2353	
Zabiullah Qomandan Kalai	854	
Mir Yanai	2065	
Badizai	3005	
Hajji Fazal Mohammad	2100	
Abdul Ghapor	1297	RC
Nawai Etifaq	1854	
Etefaq	1470	
Qumandah Zainullah	2065	
Hajji Raz Mohammad	1281	
Hajji Abdul Aziz	980	
Timor Sha	1610	
Jabar Khan Kalai	983	
Hajji Mohammad Ayob	2772	
Hajji Abdul Ghafar	973	
Kshata Bahadorzai	1941	
Hajji Nazak	2440	
Mrad Khan	2450	
Hajji Nooruldin Kalai	1481	

Mullah Abdul Kabir	1744	
Hajji Mohammad Zaman	2009	
Mirhamza Abdul Gapor	2169	34
Doctor Ahmmad	910	
Qasam Pahlawan	2895	
Ehsanullah	1631	
Hajji Alap Khan	2170	
Omar Faroq	1190	
Hajji Abdul Zahir	1715	
Hajji Abdul Qadoos	1750	
Hajji Mohammad Zai	1316	
Spin Musjad	1960	
Malim Sadullah	1995	
Hajji Musa Khan Jama	1595	
Goad Nasrullah Kalai	2051	
2 Hazrath Bilal	2210	
Roshan	2170	
Salman Farsi	1582	
Abdul Jabar Zhara Ghberga`	1566	35
Sharwal Malizai	1295	
Hajji Ram Del	1575	
Mullah Mira	3022	
Hajji Gul Agha	2135	
Hajji Qasam	2156	
Agha Mohammad Jan	1190	
Mullah Azizullah	2268	
Hajji Adam Kali	1061	
Hajji Jamal Kalai	793	
Zor Hajji Mahbob Khan	2135	
Shirindal Kalai	1053	
Hajji Tamol	1190	
Hajji Joma Khan Kalai	2100	
Doctor Quadratullah	1729	
Hajji Bagull	1806	
Hajji Fida Mohammad Kalai	1572	36
Kochnai Kaka Sadullah	1310	
Mulawi Abdullah Jan	1379	
Haji Mulla Abdul Rahman	2135	
Khalgai	1120	
Hajji Sayd Wali	1470	
Mohammad Yosaf	1190	
Mohammad Naim Kalai	1974	
Hajji Abdullah	1547	
Hajji Mohammad Yaqob	1742	
Malizai	1960	

Alam Khanzai	1680	
Jalat Khan	1706	
Hajji Noor Mohammad Khan	2240	
Loy Kariz	1540	
Samizo Kali	1925	
Glozai	1610	
Qalai Sangi Kalai		
Mohammad Lal Kalai	630	
Abdul	2044	37
Sorkai Lizhai	2345	
Amran Zai	1190	
Landai Mashingzai	1806	
Sagai	1295	
Hajji Kotan Kalai	490	
Haji kh dai Nazar	1715	
Pai Baraj	945	
Makh Gullan	938	
Sha Gullan	980	
Rabat Kalakai	1981	
Abdul Salam Zhara Ghbarga	1220	
Hajji Wali Jan	1462	
Hajji Abdul Khaliq	1884	
Hajji Mohammad Rafiq	770	
Abdul Wahab	1594	
Niko	1995	
Sorki L ezi Halim Khan	1750	
Marsinzai	1323	
Mandai Pahlawan	1960	38
Hajji Abdul Haq	1925	
Ahmmadullah Saheab Zada	2169	
Hajji Asadullah	985	
Abdul Manaf Kharzai	1697	
Madrasi Sakhidad Kalai	1050	
Adozai	2103	
Mulla Akhtar Mohammad & Haji Ghaws	1155	
Pasani (Payena) Kalai	1078	
Chodai	1801	
Hajji Mohammadin	1143	
Patankhail	1505	
Hajji Habib	1855	
Yaro Kariz	3092	
Sardi	2711	
Qazyian	2711	
Pakhwaran	1957	39
Hajji Dawood	1211	

Urozganian	932	
Targazi Kalai	1295	
Sibat Kharzai	822	
Lala Khan	2050	
Hajji Mohammad Nasim	379	
Yak Toot	606	
Hajji Salam Kalai	910	
Ali Jan Kalai	1539	
Fazal Mohammad Muslim Abad	1602	
Hajji Masod Kalai	1636	
Aminullah Kalai	1060	
Abdul Ghapor Abdul Karim Khan	508	
Firouz Kalai	1645	
Dwaham Mirajan	1982	
Lwar Kanzai	2302	
Sagar Kalai	747	
Hajji Abdullah Adozai	1820	
Kshata Hassan Zai	2205	
Mulla Abdul Rauf Tokhi Kalai	962	
Sidano Kaly	1645	RC
Hajji Sakhidad	1851	
Ahmod Jan	1505	
Zor Hajji Khodai Nazar	1764	
Abdul Wahab Raig Kalai	739	
Jag Hajji Fazal Mohammad	952	
Hajji Mullah Ahmad & Abdul Hai	1190	
Dwaham Hajji Fati Khan Kalai	736	
Mara Jan	701	
Mahmmod Khan	716	
Abdulla Kochai	1618	
Gholam Haydar	2093	
Babak Sahib Kariz	1576	
Sat Malok	2160	
Hajji Mohammad Wali	770	
Hajji Abdul Rasid	1633	
Hajji Abdul Bari Kalai	924	
Hajji Mosa Khan	1190	
Mohammad Esa Zor Rabat Kalai	1680	
Hajji Ghani	1574	
Toor Shadi	2156	40
Hajji Abdul Karim Adozai	1615	
Hajji Bahawal	895	
Hajji Barkat Adozai	1120	
Dabari	1645	
Mullah Mohammad	1288	

Shahid Lal Jan Kalai	1820	
Hajji Sha Mohammad	1190	
Hajji Wakil Samad Khan Kalai	1540	
Hajji Mado Kalai	1821	
Kamalyzi	1610	
Karhir Saminzai	1645	
Hafiz Mahmmod	595	
Abdul Shakor	2705	
Zarin	1589	
Mashi Kalai	1120	
Siuri Mear Geian	1442	
Hajji Abdul Manan	1790	
Hajji Abdullah Sa Kalai	1190	
Da Dolai Shora Rabat	2170	RC
Hajji Shahzada Shora	881	
Sopi Din Mohammad & Khodainoor	902	
Tora Ghondy	1855	
Khalifa Kalai	573	
Hajji Nadar Khan	2023	
Sara Khat	1672	
Hajji Ramazan	1236	
Payawo	1190	
Mohammad Sadat	1470	
Marjan	1961	
Shdizai	1761	
Lwar Bahadorzai	1825	
Hajji Asal	2056	
Rigi Shora	1610	
Hajji Mohammad Anwar Aka	777	
Abdul Wadood	2072	
Abdul Qadar	2062	
Hajji Akhter Mohammad	1083	41
Chogak	1258	
Qari Basir	3303	
Noor Khan	1295	
Hajji Wakil Mohammad	1470	
Hajji Nazar Dad	1872	
Hajji Allah Dad	2135	
Hajji Sadar Khan Adozai	1265	
Fatigan	972	
Saduldin	1614	
Hajji Nazar Jan Salihzai	523	
Shagai	1369	
Madina	2172	
Mohammad Arif	1470	

Hajji Raz	1803	
Abo Sa Chapawo	2126	
Konchai	1505	
Abdul Malik & Mohammad Esa	1750	42
Habibullah Kalai	582	
Hajji Lal Mohammad	1750	
Etihad Kalai	1030	
Hajji Karga Kalai	1991	
Badinzai Baz Mohammad	573	
Hajji Abdul Ghayas Khan	1085	
Naw Abad	1820	
Spina Gonbada	1659	
Hajji Niamat	1679	
Pashai	1683	
Gardai Talai	1505	
Fir Mohammad Rabat	1914	
Narat Abad	1697	
Mullah Wali Nika Wiala	1523	
Dost Mohammad	1458	
Boldakan	490	
Zara Kala Shadola	983	
Khodaidad Shir Mazai	965	
Payoo Khan	1335	
Salang Mohammad Naim	1231	
Mullah Rahmatullah	2135	43
Hajji Abdul Samad Kalai	2499	
Spin & Faizullah Khan	2163	
Samiullah	1589	
Kochnai Lahar	1297	
Walgai	1730	
Malak Bahador & Muslim Kalai	1974	
Ejansi Hajji Khodai Dad Kalai	1610	
Shir Jan	1386	
Hajji Azim Jan	2000	
Haji Wkila Kalai	1582	
Shahbudin Qalacha	420	
Haji Awrang Kalai	400	
Haji Hakim Qalacha	306	
Ali Shah Khan Qalacha	1620	
Zhor Deh	1200	
Birana	720	
Manja	762	
Haji Hayat Khan Kalai	1728	
Eid Gah	1800	44
Haji Saifuddin	1080	

Haji Peerojan	1100	
Balochan	1320	
Sardar Ayub Kalai	1130	
Haji Ghulam Dastageer Qalacha	402	
Haji Ali Mohammad Qalacha	1800	
Haji Abdul Ghafoor Qalacha	1608	
Per Agha Ziarat	600	
Haji Juma Khan Qalacha	1536	
Mula Abdul Shakoor	1560	
Qazi Nahar Qalacha	1440	
Ashogha (Malim Sarwar Khan)	1740	
Kalawal Ashugha	1320	
Da Ghrah Kalai	1770	
Kakarano Ashugha	270	
Makowan	1800	
Kuzh Ghara Kalai	1260	
Haji Abdul Qayoum	1320	
Babaran	900	
Zaidanian Kalai	900	
Kotiazai	900	
Khogani Kalai	1178	
Painda	1140	45
Tarinan Kalai	900	
Haji Baz Mohammad Kalai	1410	
Sar Takhat Kalai	1800	
Nawrozai Qalacha	240	
Najaran Qalacha	1080	
Haji Haidar Kalai	570	
Haji Abdul Wase	350	
Mir Hazar Kariz	1800	
Hassan Zo Kalai	900	
Sar Katib Kalai	1260	
Ksheta Mardan Zai	720	
Kalizai	1500	
Haji Toor Khan	1660	
Marsanzai	1854	
Loy Pul Kalai	1800	
Kodizai	1860	
Gharibano Kalai	1250	
Paikaila Kalai	1740	
Sharafuddin Kalai	1770	
Lwar Mardanzai	1530	
Omarzai	1710	46
Zor Kalai	1800	
Haji Fazal Muhammad Qalacha	1732	

Deh Gho Chak	1776	
Khanan Kalai	1720	
Lowar Ghulam Dastager	1350	
Tagiran	1500	
Abdul Wahab Kalai	1740	
Kshahat Ayobzai	1530	
Lwar Shah Bozai	1800	
Kshata Shah Bozai	1800	
Lwar Shash Bandi	1800	
Kshata Shashbandi	1740	
Ksheta Nawa Kalai	1800	
Lowar Yakalang	1560	
Lowara Nawa Kalai	1728	
Mulah Ghazi Kalai	1680	
Lawar Baghan Jai	1770	47
Ksheta Baghenjai	1800	
Ksheta Yaklang	1794	
Loy Nahre Kariz	1860	
Haji Habibullah Khan	695	
Haji Shah Jahan Kalai	1092	
Lowar Zor Kalai	554	
Nawai Kalawal	1800	
Charshakha Kalai/ Nahar Kariz	1906	
Hajji Fir Mohammad Kalai / Nalgham	1760	
Lwar Banizo Musjed/ Nahr Kariz	1315	
Salaki Kalai/Dasht	1766	
Hajji Majeed Aka Musjed/Nahar Kariz	859	
Mohammad Rauf Aka Musjed/Nahar Kariz	1250	
Mohammad Zaman Kalai/Lwar Waziran	732	
Hajji Malak Abdulla Aka Musjed	805	
Malak Baz Mohammad Kalai/ Hawz Madad	554	
Hajji Qasam Kalai/ Mishwani Howz Madad	452	
Da Zaman Agha Ghondai/ Sanzarai	663	
Nadi Dasht Kochian	1976	
Hajji Shir Mohammad Khan Kalacha/ Pashmol	457	
Hajji Abdul Razaq Kalai/Siachoi	1370	
Malang Kalacha/Pashmol	1289	
Hajji Fiaz Mohammad Aka/ Shachoi	1722	RC
Hajji Raz Mohammad Khan Kalai/Pashmol	669	
Kotwal Kalai/Pashmol	1748	
Yosaf Khan Kalai/ Pashmol	1731	
Da Ghondai Kalai/Solaghai	886	
Barakzo Kalai/Solaghai	1550	
Hajji Sardar Mohammad Kalai/ Nadi	2857	
Mahmmod Aka Kalai/Lako Khail	2132	

Hajji Abdul Rahman Kalai/ Nadi	1190	
Pasban Kalai/ Pashmol	708	
Hajji Qaysar Aka Kalai/ Lwar Nadia	901	
Hajji Ebarhim Kalai/ Nadi	1753	
Lwar Najaran Kalai	1030	
Lwar Fasal/ Qalaq	1770	
Said Jan Kalacha/Lako Khail	1905	
Hajji Raouf Kalai/Babaghdi	1204	
Mir Watak Kalai	457	
Mulla Abdul Hadi Akond Kalai/Akdahal	989	
Akhtar Mohammad Aka Kalai/Akdahal	694	
Abdul Aziz Musjed/ Dwaham Kamp	1873	
Da Shahidano Baba Da Ghra Shata Kalai/Sanzarai	1374	48
Lwar Dasht Hajji Mohammad Khan Musjed/Sanzarai	443	
Narogan Kalai/Qlaq	210	
Mashal Aka Muajed/ Saloram Kamp	452	
Abdul Salam Kalai/ Awal Kamp	666	
Dasht Kochian Yar Mohammad Aka Musjed	936	
Salo Chaman Fasal Kalai/Qalq	1017	
Abdul Salam Musjed/Draim Kamp	1412	
Hajji Fainda Muajed/ Shpazam Kamp	814	
Hajji Nik Mohammad Kalai/ Nadi	805	
Kshata Noorzai/Pashmol	274	
Mullah Abdul Ghapar Musjed/ Yawalasam Kamp	1060	
Malak Abdul Halim Kalai/Pashmol	968	
Kala Khan Kalai/ Dasht	618	
Aramzo Kalai/Salwaghai	434	
Lwar Sitaw/ Qalaq	789	
Hajji Wahab Khan Musjed	535	
Abdul Rauf Musjed/ Dasht	679	
Malak Wali Jan/Dasht	924	
Mullah Janan Musjed/ Mira Khor Dowrahi	756	
Shaista Gull Musjd/ Dasht	446	
Nasarzo Kalai/Nahar Karaiz	1052	
Hawzmadad Jama	482	
Zharai Kariz/ Sangisar	827	
Mar Khanzo Kalai / Nahri Karaiz	1512	
Da Shahid Baba Da Ghra Laman	341	
Hajji Agha Mohammad Kalai/ Hawz Madad	307	
Sra Ghondai/ Sanzarai	950	
Mirulian Musjed/ Sangisar	608	
Mullah Khawas Kalai/ Hawz Madad	818	
Mahajarin / Sangisar	1846	
Khawas Mohammad Kalai/ Howz Madad	486	
Nasrozo Kalai/ Dasht	846	

Sarkila Kalai/ Nalgham	1552	
Malangiano Kalai / Sartak	1184	
Nabatullah Kalai / Sartak	1174	49
Abdul Ahad Kalai / Sartak	280	
Ardozai Kalai/ Sartak	1840	
Mulla Wazir Akhond Kalai/ Sartak	523	
Didar Kalai/ Qalaq	635	
Hajji Mullah Gholam Haydar Akhond	1612	
Hajji Lala Jan Aka Kalai/ Kshata Nadai	1904	
Chahar Kocho/ Pashmol	1906	
Hajji Ghapar Aka Kalai/ Pashmol	480	
Hajji Khayat Kalai/ Dasht	515	
Lwara Kalacha / Sinzari Dusht	980	
Hajji Salih Mohammad Kalai/ Sartak Dasht	980	
Hajji Mohammad Rafiq Kalai/ Sartak Dasth	735	
Khalifa Said Jan Kalai/Lwar Sartak	705	
Hajji Said Mohammad Kalai/Lwar Sartak	391	
Hajji Khodai Dad Kalai/Lwar Sartak	514	
Mohammad Din Kalai/Lwar Sartak	403	
Kandahari Mama Kalai/Lwar Makwan	511	
Abdul Salam Kalai/ Lwar Dgar	910	
Wazirano Kalai/Pashmol	1580	
Kishanai Kalai/ Hawz Madad	1320	
Barj Kalai/ Hawz Madad	686	
Hajji Gholam Yahia Kalai/Lwar Mahajereen	284	
Fazal Rahman Kalai/ Lwar Mahajereen	407	
Hajji Zainuldin Kalai/Lwar Mahajarin	707	
Nik Mohammad Khan Kalai Pashmol	1304	
Hajji Shahi Aka Kalai/ Pashmol	452	
Hajji Mohammad Ewas Kalai/Kshata Nadai	1060	
Hajji Abdul Karim Kalai / Pashamol	1586	
Sadiqullah Kalai / Dasht	1850	50
Hajji Salih Mohammad Kalai / Lwar Mullayan Dasht	1831	
Fasal Kalai/ Sablaghai	1630	
Hajji Abdul Raouf Kala / Dasht	1810	
Lwar Fithawai Kalai / Sinzrai	1236	
Klak Durahi / Dasht	1385	
Hajji Dost Mohammad Kalai / Dasht	1792	
Hajji Sharif Kalai / Dasht	1772	
Fanizai Kalai/ Sartak	1772	
Diwar Kalai / Sangisar	1870	
Malak Amir Jan Kalai	490	
Garo	560	
Haji Ghulam Nabi	575	
Haji Shair Aka Kalai	2100	

Haji Nazar Aka	1400	
Haji Abdul Zaher Muhmand	670	
Haqdad Kalai	595	
Allaudin Kalai	700	
Haji Zardad Kalai	1400	
Haji Ayaz Kalai	380	
Haji Abdul Hakim	1330	
Haji Rahmatullah Kalai	1120	
Srah Ghondi	595	
Fatawi Kalai	1010	51
Gullistan Kalai	2100	
Haji Mohamood Kalai	522	
Haji Abdul Samad Kalai	1485	
Haji Ramazan Kalai	392	
Makwan	1120	
Chaghrai	380	
Mohammad Ibrahim Tarakai	1225	
Haji Amir Mohammed	392	
Wazir Khan	980	
Gezaw Tangai	466	
Abdullah Jan Kalai	350	
Hajiano Kalai	434	
Barghana	665	
Landi Kariz	350	
Bagh Kalai	350	
Sar Potakai	420	
Raz Mohammad	350	
Haji Ghulam Sarwar	385	
Haji Janan Kalai	490	
Haji Obaidullah	700	
Tawoos Khan	2100	
Abdullah Jan	560	
Hayat Khan	315	
Haji Majeed Kalai	511	
Haji Mohammad Rahim	400	
Baba Ali Kalai	700	
Akhwnd Zada	1126	
Amir Mohammad Toor Kotal	558	
Abdul Nafi	173	
Mohmand Khan	200	
Abdul Habib	864	
Malak Noor Mohammad	748	
Mohammad Tahir	524	
Showib Khan	1373	
Lwar Alizai	1288	

Kasar Kakozei	1572	
Khono Kalai	719	
Fati Khan Lwar Mail	657	52
Hajji Abdullah	318	
Said Khan Akhter Zai	1138	
Tara Balochan	499	
Hajji Mohammad Dawood	556	
Zhari Awba Mohammad Rassol	795	
Khoday Dad Aka	990	
Qabat Khan	730	
Todonkai Lwar Mail	1052	
Hajji Jalal Khan Shakarzai	149	
Hajji Mohammad Khan Naib Wala	554	
Engineer Mohammad Hassan Sardar	513	
Lawar Potaki Hajji Noor Mohammad	1392	
Geographical unit F2	Population size	Cluster
Darweshan	2163	
Balochan	1883	
Khoshi Kalai	2044	201
Kaido Kalai	2016	
Landai Now Abad	2184	
Hajji Abdul Bari Kariz	923	
Mohammad Sadiq Kariz	897	
?Qolba	979	
Wazir Kalai	511	
Hajji Dilbar Aka Kariz	704	202
Baidak	909	
China		
Jogain		
Mark		
Kshata Gull Khana		
Kalamtoo		
Bahram		
Bolagh		
Ubidullah Masom Kalai	1842	
Bidoon Sah	2329	
Singalai Kalai	1515	
Grang Sah	1713	203
Enj Sah	1997	
Asan Korai Sah	2109	
Salih Mohammad Kalai	1842	
Sardar Atha Mohammad Kalai	2058	
Moula Dad Mir Alam Ato Kalai	1814	204
Mohammad Gull Sah	2136	
Abdul Aziz Khair Aba Kalai	2096	

Par Abad Kalai	2400	
Sardar Mohammad Naim Kalai	1770	205
Abdul Halim Badur Sah	2243	
Khalifa Nik Mohammad Sirak Kalai	2050	
Abozai	1960	
Mosa Jan Agha	1381	
Shamozai	1015	
Qasemzai	713	
Torzai	1391	
Alizai	840	
Bahadurzai	1260	
Badi Karaiz	1582	
Badi Karaiz H. Rahimdad	877	
Jilao Gir	1841	
Iraqi	834	
Terwa Saan	1097	
Said Bos	1657	
Sarg	1854	
Janizai	1820	
Sahiban	1771	
Sopanzai 1	1300	
Sopanzai 2	318	
Sopanzai 3	688	
Ali Khanzai	1831	206
Isaqzai Amarat	897	
Shahabuddin	1046	
Shakrina	257	
Khogiany	980	
Da Ghra Kalai Makwan	637	
Narai Manda	1109	
Sherzo Kalai	571	
Sor Kani	1774	
Narin Wala	1148	207
Miakhanzai	650	
Payindi	700	
Kar	770	
Tisan	1103	
Shin Narai	770	
Kotizai	349	
Jamalzai	752	
Chaman Arghistan Badzai	480	
Chokazai	708	
Yaqoobzai	1078	
Sor Gaz	790	RC
Ghbarga	1123	

Awryazai	854	
Ana Khail	935	
Khalo Khail	511	
Karam Khail	996	
Bakalzai	1104	
Dawlatzai	1870	
Atmanzai	595	
Jarekzaiy	503	
Da Sar Kalai	1767	208
Malakzai	799	
Kamilzi	880	
Barizai	750	
Nasara	810	
Mamo Khail	521	
Amin Kala	1828	
ZarinZai	438	
Tahseldar Kala	494	
Ahmadzai	193	
Asakzai	528	209
Haramzai	1000	
Koghi	1250	
Tajaw	542	
Posi	832	
Bagh Kali	650	
Now Abad	630	
Sardarki	770	
Targhak (1)	500	
Targhak (2)	1050	
Haji Haqdad	260	
Haji Abdul Karim	300	
Popalzai	980	210
Landi Kali	642	
Bano Khil	1268	
Gambat	1119	
Mahraban	725	
Kakaran	210	
Karoray	650	
Spina Gara	1373	
Akhon Kalai	2215	
Sartif Kalawal Kalai	241	211
Takarai	1277	
Chaghnai Khogyanee	980	
Ali Shirzai	2034	
Nawi Pada	1010	
Habibullah	845	

Qari Abdul Bari	845	
Sar Kariz Kalai	398	
Lowar Shekhzai	1365	212
Sher Ghashtona	1533	
Degaana	1571	
Bakhora	1938	
Nari Hotak	971	
H. Kamalludin	949	
Akhto Khail	794	
Abtoo Bahlolzai	595	213
Bariwar Salimanzai	597	
Tan Kariz	873	
Sra Shela	11910	214
Faisal Karaiz	1590	
Abo Qala	966	
Ana Khail	1226	
Landai	496	215
Sor Wam	890	
Bara Khail	1423	
Tarozai	704	
Miro Khil	584	
Medizai	554	
Pialkha	359	
Sila	1507	
Sera Salai	1459	
Angizai	1132	216
Zhari Saa	1050	
Awr	1139	
Drgai	748	
Khwaja zai	1646	
Jasi	485	
Mian Kalai	2162	
Koli	1820	217
Niko Wala	2096	
Wachki	1590	
China Kalai	1246	
Ghashi	632	
Joma gul Kali	2100	
Karim Kali	1080	218
Nawi Kariz	390	
Yarokholagi	1720	
De Gharo Lower Kalai	1650	
Sahatullah Shila	1150	
Haji Abdul Karim	470	
Kando Balhol zai	1776	

Enzarwar	460	
Jalal	522	219
Kho Dai Nazar Kalai	673	
Wrazakai	744	
Barmatai	612	
Gardai Kalai	936	
Khogyanayee Hajji Bahram Khan	1154	
Lwar Lahar		
Sra Acha	694	
Sopian Kalai	812	
Tarlik Kalai	2510	
Paynawa Zamto	2671	220
Gosala	2229	
Sar Nawai & Taj Mohammad Kalai	2269	
Low Tala Kalai	3812	221
Kortai Kalai	2447	
Pay Draskol Kalai	3219	
Mazar Kalai Shora	2274	RC
Mullah Mohammad Zai Kalai	2842	
Ghilang Kalai	2514	
Chako Gak	2693	222
Niamat Kalai	2729	
Hajji Mohammad Salim Agha	2742	
Dinar Khail	866	
Karizgai	1073	
Sardagh	1427	223
Barika	1732	
Ghoi Matan	1955	
Shin Lita	725	
Pakha Cheena	639	
Sayad Kariz	1247	
Sar Poshan	500	
Kochnai Kariz	1142	224
Turkman	1053	
Chopani	823	
Haji Alam	1350	
Haji Mohammad Zai	1075	
Jamak	778	
Lowar Gonbad	1308	
Kshata Gashta	633	
Gardi China	618	
Podina	1610	RC
Nanai Kalai	2184	

Questionnaire's training

Extreme MUAC

Security briefing: approaching roads

Data entry team